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Thermal and Multiphase Validations with the Lattice Boltzmann Method Software XFlow

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List of Acronyms

BE Boltzmann Equation

BBGKY Bogoliubov, Born, Green, Kirkwood and Yvon

BGK Approximation of the collision term by Bhatnagar, Gross and Krook

CESGA CEntro de Supercomputacion de GAlicia (Galician supercomputing center)

CFD Computational Fluid Dynamics

CFL Courant-Friedrich-Levy

C-H Cahn-Hilliard

ELBE Entropic Lattice Boltzmann Method

LBE Lattice Boltzmann Equation

LBGK LBE with BGK approximation

LBM Lattice Boltzmann Method

LES Large-Eddy Simulation

LGA Lattice Gas Automata

LODI Locally One-Dimensional Inviscid

MPI Message Passing Interface

MRT Multiple Relaxation Time

NEA Nuclear Energy Agency

N-S Navier-Stokes

OECD Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

SRT Single Relaxation Time

VOF Volume Of Fluid

WALE Wall-Adapting Local Eddy

Abstract

English

In this work a series of thermal and multiphase validation tests carried out with the CFD software XFlow is presented. Furthermore, a complete introduction to the lattice Boltzmann method, the numerical core of XFlow, is included.

The obtained numerical results show a mixed success, indicating a need for further enhancements in the implementation of the different numerical solvers involved.

Galego

Neste traballo preséntase unha serie de validacións numéricas e experimentais de simulacións térmicas e multifase levadas a cabo co software CFD XFlow. Ademáis, inclúese unha introdución teórica ao método lattice Boltzmann, esquema numérico no que se basea XFlow.

Os resultados obtidos son mixtos en xeral, indicando a necesidade de seguir realizando melloras nos diferentes solvers numéricos empregados.

Castellano

En este trabajo se presenta una serie de validaciones numéricas y experimentales de simulaciones térmicas y multifase realizadas con el software CFD

XFlow. Además, se incluye una introducción teórica al método lattice Boltzmann, esquema numérico en el que se basa XFlow.

Los resultados obtenidos han sido mixtos en general, indicando la necesidad de seguir realizando mejoras en los diferentes solvers numéricos empleados.

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Introduction

The topic for this master's thesis was proposed by the Spanish company Next Limit Technologies, developer of the software XFlow™ for Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). This is a relatively young code whose novelty lies in its numerical implementation, which is based in the so-called lattice Boltzmann method, a scheme based on principles from statistical physics and kinetic theory which can be seen as a discretization of the Boltzmann equation, as opposed to a typical Navier-Stokes solver.

The proposed work consists, basically, in performing a series of simulations aimed to analyze the performance of the software in thermal and multiphase problems. These simulations are backed up with existing experimental and numerical data against which the results produced with XFlow can be compared and validated.

The first test case is based on a benchmark exercise proposed in 2009 by the OECD¹ Nuclear Energy Agency [47], and consists in a simulation of thermal mixing between a hot and a cold inlet in a T-Junction, where several temperature and velocity profiles have to be measured and compared against experimental data. The original purpose of this benchmark was to test the performance of existing CFD codes in predicting a set of important parameters affecting thermal fatigue in T-Junctions. Here, the experimental data will be used to validate the results produced by XFlow.

On the other side, the simulations aimed to test the multiphase solver are based on two benchmarks proposed in a series of articles, and consist on the simulation of a rising bubble [25] and a Rayleigh-Taylor instability [56], [19], [12]. For these two test cases there is no experimental data available, but there are plenty of numerical results produced by other codes that can be used to compare against the XFlow simulations.

To be able to run more refined and computing demanding simulations we

¹Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development.

contacted with the CESGA², that kindly gave us access to its computational resources.

The present work is divided into three main sections: first, a theoretical introduction to the lattice Boltzmann method and its fundamental principles is given; then, a second chapter briefly presents the most important aspects of XFlow; and, finally, a third section is devoted to the performed simulations, their description, numerical results and conclusions.

²Galician supercomputing center. From Spanish: CEntro de Supercomputación de GALicia.

Chapter 1

The Lattice Boltzmann Method

The mathematical modeling of a fluid is a complex task. In classical physics a fluid might be considered as a system of N particles or “billiard balls” that move in space and collide with each other. This **microscopic** description gives rise to a number of equations equal to the number of particles in the fluid, and all of them have to be solved in order to obtain the evolution of the system. This is not possible in general (computationally speaking) because in a typical problem one has a quantity of particles of the order of Avogadro’s number (10^{23}).

To avoid this microscopic complexity one usually turns to the Navier-Stokes equations, which give a description of the fluid in terms of **macroscopic** quantities such as density, velocity or temperature. The problem of this model is that the equations are nonlinear and require numerical methods to be solved. Furthermore, they are only valid in situations with small Knudsen number¹ ($\text{Kn} \ll 1$) and, because of their macroscopic description, fail in problems where the microscopic interactions in the fluid are not negligible, that is, problems where the characteristic distance is similar or smaller than the mean free path of the particles in the fluid (i.e. microfluidics, MEMS², etc.).

As a result, one might prefer to go back to a microscopic description, where the equations are simpler and the small scale interactions between the particles can be taken into account. However, one still has the problem of having an enormous amount of equations to solve, and this is where the

¹The Knudsen number $\text{Kn} = \frac{\lambda}{L}$ is the ratio between the mean free path of a particle in the fluid and the characteristic length of the system.

²MEMS: Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems

Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) comes in.

The LBM is a numerical scheme based on a discretization of the Boltzmann equation (a microscopic description of a gas) where, instead of taking into account all the molecules in the fluid, only a number of “macromolecules” is considered. Because of this, the LBM is usually referred to as a **mesoscopic** model.

The main idea behind this approach is that one does not need to take into account every single molecule of a fluid in order to recover a correct solution at a macroscopic level. Furthermore, and even more importantly, one does not need to describe all the microscopic details of the molecules and their complicated interactions with each other in order to obtain an accurate macroscopic solution. Citing R. P. Feynman in [58]:

“We have noticed in nature that the behavior of a fluid depends very little on the nature of the individual particles in that fluid. For example, the flow of sand is very similar to the flow of water or the flow of a pile of ball bearings. We have therefore taken advantage of this fact to invent a type of imaginary particle that is especially simple for us to simulate. This particle is a perfect ball bearing that can move at a single speed in one of six directions. The flow of these particles on a large enough scale is very similar to the flow of natural fluids.”

He was talking here about the Lattice Gas Automata (LGA) [16], the historical predecessor of the LBM, which was a simpler and less sophisticated model than the LBM of today, but still serves to illustrate the main ideas behind this method.

In the last decade, the LBM has achieved great success in the field of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), with promising results even in problems with high Knudsen numbers.

The LBM is sometimes introduced from a historical point of view as the evolution of the LGA (that evolved itself from the Cellular Automata of the 50s). This is not the purpose of this work. In the current chapter, a first section will be dedicated to mathematically deduce and better understand the Boltzmann Equation (BE), from which the equations of the LBM will be directly obtained. Then, it will also be proven, by means of the Chapman-Enskog expansion, that the LBM is indeed a method that correctly reproduces the macroscopic behavior of a fluid. Finally, an application of the LBM

to multiphase fluids will be presented (that is, the numerical solution of the Cahn-Hilliard equation).

1.1 Finding the Boltzmann Equation

The Boltzmann equation is a fundamental piece of statistical physics. It describes the evolution of a rarefied³ gas from a statistical point of view by means of the one-particle distribution function. This is a function $f_1 = f_1(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, t)$ that gives the probability $f_1 = f_1(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, t)d\mathbf{q}d\mathbf{p}$ of finding one particle in the position interval $[\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q} + d\mathbf{q}]$, with momentum in $[\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p} + d\mathbf{p}]$, at time t with all the other particles being in any other position.

This function does not contain all the information in the gas, it is a simplification of a more complex problem. A complete description of a gas (any gas, not just a rarefied one) of N particles would require a N -particle distribution function $f_N = f_N(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t)$ that gives the probability

$$f_N(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t)d\mathbf{q}_1d\mathbf{p}_1d\mathbf{q}_2d\mathbf{p}_2 \cdots d\mathbf{q}_Nd\mathbf{p}_N$$

of finding, at time t , one particle in position $[\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{q}_1 + d\mathbf{q}_1]$, with momentum $[\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_1 + d\mathbf{p}_1]$ and another particle in position $[\mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{q}_2 + d\mathbf{q}_2]$, with momentum $[\mathbf{p}_2, \mathbf{p}_2 + d\mathbf{p}_2]$ and a third particle in $([\mathbf{q}_3, \mathbf{q}_3 + d\mathbf{q}_3])$ and so on, until the N -th particle. This function would contain all the information in the gas, but, as previously stated, such approach is not feasible due to the enormous amount of molecules found in a typical gas.

In this section, the Boltzmann equation will be deduced from the more general equation for the N -particle distribution function. All the material presented here is based on references [32], [60], [6], [29], [35] and [18].

1.1.1 The Hamiltonian description of a mechanical system

In Hamiltonian Mechanics, the description of a system of N particles is no longer limited to the use of the Euclidean position and velocity coordinates. It is a different formulation of Classical Mechanics in which each particle is characterized by a set of coordinates, subject to no restriction, called canonical coordinates: the canonical position \mathbf{q} and the canonical momentum \mathbf{p} .

³A rarefied or diluted gas is defined as a gas whose pressure is much less than the atmospheric pressure.

This set of coordinates defines the *phase space* in which the system will evolve in time. For a system of N particles in three dimensions a total of $6N$ coordinates is needed (each particle needs 3 coordinates for the momentum and 3 for the position).

A mechanical system is characterized by a function called the Hamiltonian, which in some usual cases corresponds to its total energy. For example, a system of N noninteracting particles subject to an external potential \mathcal{U} has a Hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_i^2}{2m} + \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_i) \right). \quad (1.1)$$

The evolution of a system is then determined by the equations of motion for \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{p} (the Hamilton's equations), which are related to the functional \mathcal{H} by means of

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i = \frac{\partial \mathcal{H}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\text{and } \dot{\mathbf{p}}_i = -\frac{\partial \mathcal{H}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i}, \quad (1.3)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i$ and $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_i$ are the total time derivatives of \mathbf{q}_i and \mathbf{p}_i .

Now, the key part here is that the evolution in time of any function $f = f(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{p}_i, t)$ can be written in terms of the Hamiltonian in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{df}{dt} &= \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \dot{\mathbf{q}}_i + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} \dot{\mathbf{p}}_i = \\ &= \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \dot{\mathbf{q}}_i + \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} \dot{\mathbf{p}}_i \right) = \\ &= \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \frac{\partial \mathcal{H}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} - \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} \frac{\partial \mathcal{H}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \right) = \\ &= \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + [f, \mathcal{H}], \end{aligned} \quad (1.4)$$

where the third line was obtained by substituting the Hamilton's equations (1.2) and (1.3), and in the last equality the Poisson bracket formalism was

used⁴.

The quantities that remain constant in time as the system evolves are called *integrals of motion*, and for f to be an integral of motion it must verify

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + [f, \mathcal{H}] = 0 . \quad (1.5)$$

Furthermore, if f does not explicitly depend on time, this condition is reduced to:

$$[f, \mathcal{H}] = 0 . \quad (1.6)$$

1.1.2 Liouville's theorem

As previously said, the state of a gas can be completely determined by a N -particle distribution function. What the Liouville's theorem claims is, basically, that

$$f_N(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t)$$

is an integral of motion, which means that its evolution is governed by the equation

$$\frac{\partial f_N}{\partial t} + [f_N, \mathcal{H}] = 0, \quad (1.7)$$

or, more explicitly,

$$\frac{\partial f_N}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial f_N}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \frac{\partial \mathcal{H}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} - \frac{\partial f_N}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} \frac{\partial \mathcal{H}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \right) = 0 . \quad (1.8)$$

This is called the Liouville equation.

The full phase space density f_N contains, however, much more information than needed in order to give an accurate enough description of the system, and some approximations can be made in order to find a simpler model. In particular, it is usually enough to consider only the one-particle or the two-particle distribution functions, instead of f_N . For example, the Boltzmann equation is only for the one-particle distribution function. The first step towards this simplification is the so-called BBGKY hierarchy.

⁴The Poisson bracket of two functions f and g is defined as

$$[f, g] = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} - \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{p}_i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \right)$$

1.1.3 The BBGKY hierarchy

A one-particle distribution function refers to the probability

$$f_1 = f_1(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, t) d\mathbf{q} d\mathbf{p}$$

of finding any of the N particles in position \mathbf{q} , with momentum \mathbf{p} , at time t . In other words, it is the *expectation value* of finding a particle in (\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) :

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, t) &= \langle \delta^3(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_1) \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_1) + \dots + \delta^3(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_N) \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_N) \rangle = \\ &= \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^N \delta^3(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_i) \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i) \right\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N \langle \delta^3(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_i) \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i) \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (1.9)$$

where δ^3 is the delta function in three dimensions.

Here, each of the terms in the summation is the expectation value of finding particle 1, or particle 2, ..., or particle N in (\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) , and it is related to the full phase space distribution function in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \delta^3(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_1) \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_1) \rangle &= \int f_N(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t) d\mathbf{q}_2 d\mathbf{p}_2 d\mathbf{q}_3 d\mathbf{p}_3 \cdots d\mathbf{q}_N d\mathbf{p}_N \\ \langle \delta^3(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_2) \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_2) \rangle &= \int f_N(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t) d\mathbf{q}_1 d\mathbf{p}_1 d\mathbf{q}_3 d\mathbf{p}_3 \cdots d\mathbf{q}_N d\mathbf{p}_N \\ &\vdots \\ \langle \delta^3(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_N) \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_N) \rangle &= \int f_N(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, t) d\mathbf{q}_1 d\mathbf{p}_1 \cdots d\mathbf{q}_{N-1} d\mathbf{p}_{N-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.10)$$

The integrals represent the probability of finding particle i in (\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) with the other particles being located at any other point in the whole domain.

The key assumption here is that f_N is symmetric with respect to particle permutations, which means that all of the N integrals above are identical. Because of this, f_1 can be written as:

$$f_1(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, t) = N \int f_N(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t) d\mathbf{q}_2 d\mathbf{p}_2 d\mathbf{q}_3 d\mathbf{p}_3 \cdots d\mathbf{q}_N d\mathbf{p}_N. \quad (1.11)$$

The same can be done for the two-particle distribution function, which would be

$$f_2(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, t) = N(N-1) \int f_N(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t) d\mathbf{q}_3 d\mathbf{p}_3 \cdots d\mathbf{q}_N d\mathbf{p}_N. \quad (1.12)$$

And, in general, for the s -particle distribution function ($1 \leq s \leq N$):

$$f_s(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{q}_s, \mathbf{p}_s t) = \frac{N!}{(N-s)!} \int f_N(\mathbf{q}_{s+1}, \mathbf{p}_{s+1}, \dots, \mathbf{q}_N, \mathbf{p}_N, t) d\mathbf{q}_{s+1} d\mathbf{p}_{s+1} \cdots d\mathbf{q}_N d\mathbf{p}_N. \quad (1.13)$$

Therefore, reduced s -particle distribution functions can be easily found from f_N . One important remark is that while f_N is normalized to 1, the functions f_s are normalized to $\frac{N!}{(N-s)!}$.

The next step is to find the time evolution of these functions, which is given by:

$$\frac{\partial f_s}{\partial t} = \frac{N!}{(N-s)!} \int \frac{\partial f_N}{\partial t} d\mathbf{q}_{s+1} d\mathbf{p}_{s+1} \cdots d\mathbf{q}_N d\mathbf{p}_N, \quad (1.14)$$

and, by using the Liouville equation (1.7) for f_N :

$$\frac{\partial f_s}{\partial t} = -\frac{N!}{(N-s)!} \int [f_N, \mathcal{H}] d\mathbf{q}_{s+1} d\mathbf{p}_{s+1} \cdots d\mathbf{q}_N d\mathbf{p}_N. \quad (1.15)$$

To solve the integral in the right-hand side, an expression for the Hamiltonian of the system is needed. In order to find \mathcal{H} , the following assumptions will be made:

1. The system of particles can be subjected to an external potential \mathcal{U} , which depends only on the position.
2. Only two-particle interactions will be considered. In principle, this is only valid for dilute (rarefied) gases, since for more dense fluids three and higher body interactions become more important.
3. The external forces do not affect the interactions (collisions) between the particles.

With this assumptions in mind, the Hamiltonian of the system is:

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_i^2}{2m} + \underbrace{\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_i)}_{\text{external potential}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j)=1}^N \underbrace{\nu(\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{q}_j)}_{\text{two-body interaction}}. \quad (1.16)$$

For calculating the integral above, it is useful to divide the Hamiltonian into:

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_s + \mathcal{H}_{N-s} + \mathcal{H}', \quad (1.17)$$

where \mathcal{H}_s and \mathcal{H}_{N-s} include only interactions among each group of particles

$$\mathcal{H}_s = \sum_{n=1}^s \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_n^2}{2m} + \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_n) \right) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(n,m)=1}^s \nu(\mathbf{q}_n - \mathbf{q}_m). \quad (1.18)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_{N-s} = \sum_{i=s+1}^N \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_i^2}{2m} + \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_i) \right) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j)=s+1}^N \nu(\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{q}_j). \quad (1.19)$$

while the interparticle interactions are contained in \mathcal{H}'

$$\mathcal{H}' = \sum_{n=1}^s \sum_{i=s+1}^N \nu(\mathbf{q}_n - \mathbf{q}_i). \quad (1.20)$$

Substituting these expressions in (1.15), one finally finds that the evolution of f_s is governed by:

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial f_s}{\partial t} + [f_s, \mathcal{H}_s]}_{\text{streaming terms}} = \underbrace{\sum_{n=1}^s \int \frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_n - \mathbf{q}_{s+1})}{\partial \mathbf{q}_n} \frac{\partial f_{s+1}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} d\mathbf{q}_{s+1} d\mathbf{p}_{s+1}}_{\text{collision term}}. \quad (1.21)$$

In the absence of interactions with other particles, the distribution function f_s for a group of s particles would evolve as the distribution function of an incompressible fluid (like f_N in (1.15)), that is, it would only be described by the *streaming terms*.

However, the group of s particles is only a subset of the total N particles and, thus, its motion will be affected by the presence of the other $N - s$ particles. This is why the flow is modified by the *collision term*.

The collision integral is the sum of the terms corresponding to a potential collision between any of the particles in the group of s and one of the remaining $N - s$ particles.

It can be seen in equation (1.21) that, in order to find f_s , one first needs to know f_{s+1} . This means that calculating f_1 requires f_2 , which also requires $f_3 \dots$ and so on, until f_N . This chain of equations is known as BBGKY hierarchy⁵ and needs to be truncated at some level in order to get approximate solutions.

⁵Named BBGKY after its authors: Bogoliubov, Born, Green, Kirkwood and Yvon.

The BBGKY hierarchy can also be written in a more extended way as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f_s}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^s \frac{\mathbf{p}_i}{m} \frac{\partial f_s}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} + \sum_{i=1}^s \left(-\frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} - \sum_{j=1}^s \frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{q}_j)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_i} \right) = \\ \sum_{n=1}^s \int \frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_n - \mathbf{q}_{s+1})}{\partial \mathbf{q}_n} \frac{\partial f_{s+1}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} d\mathbf{q}_{s+1} d\mathbf{p}_{s+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.22)$$

1.1.4 The Boltzmann equation

A suitable approximation can be obtained by estimating the relative importance of the different terms appearing in the first two equations of the hierarchy:

- $s = 1$:

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \frac{\mathbf{p}_1}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_1)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} \right] f_1 = \int \frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_1 - \mathbf{q}_2)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} d\mathbf{q}_2 d\mathbf{p}_2. \quad (1.23)$$

- $s = 2$:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \frac{\mathbf{p}_1}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} + \frac{\mathbf{p}_2}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}_2} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_1)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_2)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_2} - \frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_1 - \mathbf{q}_2)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_2} \right) \right] f_2 = \\ = \int \left[\frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_1 - \mathbf{q}_3)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} + \frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_2 - \mathbf{q}_3)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_2} \right] f_3 d\mathbf{q}_3 d\mathbf{p}_3. \end{aligned} \quad (1.24)$$

All the terms in brackets have units of s^{-1} (inverse of time), and their relative importance can be estimated by dimensional analysis using typical velocities and length scales

- Terms with the external potential:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q})}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \sim \frac{1}{\tau_U} \sim \frac{v}{L} \sim 10^5 s^{-1} \Rightarrow \tau_U \sim 10^{-5} \text{ s}. \quad (1.25)$$

This term involves spatial variations of the potential $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q})$, which typically take place over macroscopic distances $L \sim 10^{-3}$ m, while the typical speed of a gas particle at room temperature is $v \sim 10^2$ ms $^{-1}$.

- Collision terms in the left-hand side:

$$\frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q})}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \sim \frac{1}{\tau_C} \sim \frac{v}{\lambda} \sim 10^{12} \text{s}^{-1} \Rightarrow \tau_C \sim 10^{-12} \text{ s}. \quad (1.26)$$

This term involves spatial variations of the inter-atomic potential ν which, for short-range interactions, have a typical distance of $\lambda \sim 10^{-10}$ m. From here the collision time τ_C is obtained.

- Collision terms in the right-hand side:

$$\int \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q})}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \frac{f_{s+1}}{f_s} \sim \frac{1}{\tau_X}. \quad (1.27)$$

The integral is basically zero outside a volume d^3 on the inter-atomic potential, and the term $\frac{f_{s+1}}{f_s}$ is related to the probability of finding another particle per unit of volume, which is roughly the particle density $n = \frac{N}{v} \sim 10^{26}$. τ_X is the time between collisions.

$$\frac{1}{\tau_X} \sim d^3 \frac{1}{\tau_C} n \sim 10^8 \text{s}^{-1} \Rightarrow \tau_X \sim 10^{-8} \text{ s}. \quad (1.28)$$

So, for short range interactions $\tau_C \sim 10^{-12}$ s, which implies that

$$\tau_C \ll \tau_X \Rightarrow \frac{\tau_C}{\tau_X} \sim nd^3 \ll 1. \quad (1.29)$$

This is the approximation needed to obtain the Boltzmann equation.

Because of this condition, the terms in the right-hand side of equation (1.24) are going to be smaller than the left-hand side by a factor $nd^3 \sim 10^{-4}$. This happens for all the equations in the BBGKY hierarchy except for the first one ($s = 1$), so setting the right-hand side to zero in the second equation ($s = 2$) is a good approximation in general, breaking the chain of equations:

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \frac{\mathbf{p}_1}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} + \frac{\mathbf{p}_2}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}_2} - \frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_1 - \mathbf{q}_2)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_2} \right) \right] f_2 = 0. \quad (1.30)$$

Furthermore, for time scales longer than τ_C it can be assumed that f_2 is stationary ($\frac{\partial f_2}{\partial t} = 0$). It is also expected that f_2 will have slow variations

over the center of mass coordinate $\mathbf{Q} = \frac{\mathbf{q}_1 + \mathbf{q}_2}{2}$ and large variations over the relative coordinate $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_2 - \mathbf{q}_1$:

$$\frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{Q}} \ll \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{q}}, \quad (1.31)$$

$$\frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{q}_2} \approx \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \approx \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{q}}, \quad (1.32)$$

and, under this assumption, (1.30) can be expressed as

$$\frac{\partial \nu(\mathbf{q}_1 - \mathbf{q}_2)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_2} \right) f_2 = - \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2}{m} \right) \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{q}}, \quad (1.33)$$

which can be substituted into the collision term of the equation for $s = 1$ (1.23) to find:

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \frac{\mathbf{p}_1}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_1)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} \right] f_1 = \int \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_2 - \mathbf{p}_1}{m} \right) \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \mathbf{q}} d\mathbf{q}_2 d\mathbf{p}_2. \quad (1.34)$$

This is already very close to the Boltzmann equation. Now, by doing a series of transformations to the collision term involving the scattering of the two colliding particles (regarded as spheres), the integral can be rewritten as

$$\text{COLL} = \int d^3 \mathbf{p}_2 d^2 \Omega \left| \frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right| |\mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{v}_2| [f_2(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}'_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}'_2, t) - f_2(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, t)], \quad (1.35)$$

where Ω is the solid angle, $\left| \frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right|$ is the differential cross section and $\mathbf{p}'_1, \mathbf{p}'_2$ and $\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_2$ are the moments of the particle before and after the collision.

The problem is that f_2 is still in the equation, and some approximation is needed in order to obtain an expression for it. Here is where Boltzmann comes in. He assumed that, prior to the collision, the two particles are uncorrelated. This is the famous *stosszahlansatz* or molecular chaos assumption, and allows f_2 to be written as

$$f_2(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, t) = f_1(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, t) f_1(\mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, t), \quad (1.36)$$

and by substituting this into equation (1.34) one finally finds the Boltzmann equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \frac{\mathbf{p}_1}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{q}_1)}{\partial \mathbf{q}_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} \right] f_1 = \\ & = \int d^3 \mathbf{p}_2 d^2 \Omega \left| \frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right| |\mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{v}_2| [f_1(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}'_1, t) f_1(\mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}'_2, t) - f_1(\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{p}_1, t) f_1(\mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{p}_2, t)], \end{aligned} \quad (1.37)$$

which is usually written in a more compact way as:

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla f = Q(f, f), \quad (1.38)$$

where the f_1 is now called f for simplicity, and $\mathbf{v} = (\dot{\mathbf{q}}, \dot{\mathbf{p}})$.

1.1.5 Summary

The main ideas of this section can be visualized in the following diagram:

The following section will be dedicated to the study of the Boltzmann equation, and some of its most important features, implications and characteristics will be presented.

1.2 Studying the Boltzmann Equation

As seen in the previous section, the Boltzmann equation (BE)

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \nabla f = Q(f, f) \quad (1.39)$$

describes the evolution of a rarefied gas by means of the one-particle distribution function, under the assumptions that only two-particle collisions are happening (and are not influenced by external forces) and that the two colliding particles are uncorrelated prior to the collision (molecular chaos assumption).

In this section, which is mainly based on Ref. [60], some key properties of the BE are going to be briefly discussed because of their importance for the numerical schemes that will be later described.

Also, from now on, the chosen coordinates are going to be $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{q}$ and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{p}/m$, so that $f = f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$.

1.2.1 Collision invariants

A collision invariant is defined as a quantity $\psi(\mathbf{v})$ that verifies

$$\int Q(f, f)\psi(\mathbf{v})d^3v = 0, \quad (1.40)$$

and it can be shown that, in the three-dimensional case, there exist 5 elementary collision invariants $\psi_k(\mathbf{v})$ ($k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$):

$$\psi_0 = 1, \quad (1.41)$$

$$\psi_i = v_i \quad (i = 1, 2, 3), \quad (1.42)$$

$$\psi_4 = v^2, \quad (1.43)$$

which, multiplied by the mass m , correspond to the mass (ψ_0), the momentum (ψ_1, ψ_2, ψ_3) and the energy (ψ_4).

1.2.2 H-Theorem and equilibrium

The H-Theorem is, perhaps, the most controversial result within the BE theory. It establishes that there is a quantity H , defined as

$$H := \int f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) \ln f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3x d^3v, \quad (1.44)$$

that cannot decrease in time, namely

$$\frac{dH}{dt} \geq 0, \quad (1.45)$$

with the equal sign only in the case that $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ is a Maxwell distribution

$$f^M(\mathbf{v}) = C e^{\frac{m(\mathbf{v}^2 - \mathbf{u}^2)}{2k_B T}} , \quad (1.46)$$

which is the velocity distribution for an ideal gas, and where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and C , T and \mathbf{u} are constants too.

This result implies that there is some kind of *irreversibility* in the system that causes H to increase in time. This was, and still is, a striking result, because the laws that govern the system at a microscopic scale are time-reversible. H is usually identified with the thermodynamic entropy, and this theorem represented the unification of two previously separated fields: thermodynamics and mechanics.

The direct implication of this theorem is that as time goes by (and collisions happen) the distribution function will tend to a Maxwellian distribution function, so that, as $t \rightarrow \infty$, $f \rightarrow f^M$. This implies that the Maxwellian is the equilibrium distribution function.

1.2.3 Approximation of the collision term

The biggest problem when solving the BE is the complexity of the collision operator $Q(f, f)$. It is therefore expected that some approximations have been developed in order to simplify this term.

These approximations are based on two key assumptions:

- The large amount of detail of the two-body interactions can be reduced without having a significant impact over macroscopic variables.
- The effect of the collisions in the gas is to bring the distribution function f closer to the equilibrium, i.e., to the Maxwellian distribution f^M . In other words, $Q(f, f)$ should make $f \rightarrow f^M$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

There are several ways of approximating $Q(f, f)$, but all of them have to:

- Verify the H-Theorem.
- Preserve the 5 collision invariants.

The most widely used approximation, because of its simplicity, is the BGK⁶ approximation:

$$Q(f, f) = \frac{1}{\tau} (f^M(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) - f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)) . \quad (1.47)$$

⁶Named BGK after its authors: Bhatnagar, Gross and Krook.

This is a linearization of the collision term around the equilibrium, where τ is known as the *relaxation time*, a measure of how fast does $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ tend to the equilibrium distribution $f^M(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$, and it is related to the viscosity of the fluid through

$$\nu = c_s^2 \left(\tau - \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad (1.48)$$

where c_s is the speed of sound.

1.2.4 Obtaining the macroscopic variables

Solving the BE provides a distribution function $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ but, for any practical applications, one is usually interested in measurable quantities such as density, velocity and energy. All of them can be computed by using the velocity moments of the distribution function:

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = m \int f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3v, \quad (1.49)$$

$$\rho \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = m \int f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) \mathbf{v} d^3v, \quad (1.50)$$

$$\rho e(\mathbf{x}, t) = m \int f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) \frac{\mathbf{v}^2}{2} d^3v, \quad (1.51)$$

where d^3v stands for $dv_x dv_y dv_z$, m is the particle mass and $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ is normalized to give a density of particles.

1.2.5 The Chapman-Enskog expansion

Macroscopic variables are, then, easy to compute, but how can one be sure that their evolution is correct? Is the BE really a good model for fluid dynamics? The answer is yes. The conservation equations for mass, momentum and energy are easily obtained from the BE and, from them, by means of the Chapman-Enskog expansion, the Navier-Stokes equations can be recovered.

The derivation of the Navier-Stokes equations goes as follows. First, the conservation laws can be obtained by multiplying the BE by the collision invariants ψ_k and integrating in the velocity space. By doing this, the collision term vanishes by definition (1.40) and the BE reads:

$$\int \psi_k \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + v_\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\alpha} \right) f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3v = 0, \quad (1.52)$$

where $\alpha = 1, 2, 3$ for the 3D case. In this way, the conservation laws for mass ($\psi_1 = 1$), momentum ($\psi_\alpha = v_\alpha$) and energy ($\psi_4 = \frac{1}{2}m |\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}|$) are obtained:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\alpha}(\rho u_\alpha) = 0, \quad (1.53)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial u_\alpha}{\partial t} + \rho u_\beta \frac{\partial u_\alpha}{\partial x_\beta} = -\frac{\partial \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_\beta}, \quad (1.54)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \rho u_\beta \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_\beta} = -\frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial q_\alpha}{\partial x_\alpha} - \frac{2}{3} \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta} \Lambda_{\alpha\beta}, \quad (1.55)$$

where

$$n(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3v, \quad (1.56)$$

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = m n(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (1.57)$$

$$\rho u_\alpha(\mathbf{x}, t) = m \int v_\alpha f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3v, \quad (1.58)$$

$$\theta(\mathbf{x}, t) = k_B T(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{m}{3m} \int (v_\alpha - u_\alpha)(v_\alpha - u_\alpha) f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3v, \quad (1.59)$$

$$\Lambda_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_\alpha}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\partial u_\beta}{\partial x_\alpha} \right), \quad (1.60)$$

$$\hat{P}_{\alpha\beta} = m \int (v_\alpha - u_\alpha)(v_\beta - u_\beta) f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3v, \quad (1.61)$$

$$q_\alpha(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{m^2}{2} \int (v_\alpha - u_\alpha)(v_\beta - u_\beta)(v_\beta - u_\beta) f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3v. \quad (1.62)$$

The equations (1.53) to (1.55) are useless if one does not know $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$, for which the BE has to be solved. This is made by using the Chapman-Enskog expansion:

$$f = f^{(0)} + \epsilon f^{(1)} + \epsilon^2 f^{(2)} + \dots, \quad (1.63)$$

where the distribution function is expanded around the equilibrium (that is $f^{(0)} = f^M$) and ϵ is a small parameter ($\epsilon \ll 1$) which corresponds to the Knudsen number. This means that this expansion is only valid for systems where the Knudsen number is small, which are the systems that can be described macroscopically with the Navier-Stokes equations. Other expansions for cases where the Knudsen number is larger do also exist [6].

From this point the calculations are rather involved, and here only some results will be given. Considering the BE with the BGK collision term, the

expansion (1.63) yields the following equations for zero and first order:

$$f^{(0)} = f^M, \quad (1.64)$$

$$f^{(1)} = -\tau \left(\frac{\partial^{(1)}}{\partial t} f^{(0)} + v_\alpha \frac{\partial^{(1)}}{\partial x_\alpha} f^{(0)} \right) \quad (1.65)$$

Introducing $f^{(0)} = f^M$ into the conservation laws one finds the Euler equations and, by continuing to first order, the Navier-Stokes equations appear.

1.3 The Lattice Boltzmann Equation

The Chapman-Enskog expansion demonstrates the ability of the BE to model fluid dynamics. This opens the way for an alternative approach to simulate fluids. Instead of trying to discretize the continuity, Navier-Stokes and heat equations directly, a simple discretization of the Boltzmann equation suffices.

The discretized BE is known as the Lattice Boltzmann Equation (LBE), and the numerical scheme born from it is known as the Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM). This method consists, basically, on discretizing the space into a *lattice* of nodes and the reduction of the velocity space into only a few possible velocities, namely, the velocities needed for one particle to move from its node to one of its neighboring nodes in one time step. An example of this can be seen in figure 1.1.

In this section the LBE is going to be derived from the BE, and the LBM will be presented and studied.

1.3.1 Derivation of the LBE

For the sake of simplicity, and based on Ref. [60], the LBE is going to be derived here from the BE with BGK approximation and under the assumption of no external forces. However, other approximations for the collision term can be used, and some alternatives will be later presented.

The BE with BGK approximation reads

$$\frac{\partial f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) = \frac{1}{\tau} (f^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t) - f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)) . \quad (1.66)$$

The first step is to discretize the velocity space into a subset of v_i velocities, each of them governed by a distribution function $f_i = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$ that obeys

$$\frac{\partial f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \nabla f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\tau} (f_i^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)) . \quad (1.67)$$

Figure 1.1: The D3Q27 Lattice Boltzmann scheme. In this three dimensional scheme the particles can only travel from its node (in the center) to other 26 positions in the next time step. This allows a total of 27 velocities considering the possibility that particles can be at rest. Picture taken from ref. [51].

This is the *discrete Boltzmann equation*, which can be nondimensionalized by the characteristic length scale, L , the reference speed, U , the reference density, n_r , and the time between particle collisions, t_c , finding:

$$\frac{\partial F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t})}{\partial \hat{t}} + \mathbf{c}_i \hat{\nabla} F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t}) = \frac{1}{\hat{\tau} \epsilon} \left(F_i^{(eq)}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t}) \right), \quad (1.68)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{x}/L$, $\mathbf{c}_i = \mathbf{v}_i/U$, $\hat{\nabla} = L\nabla$, $\hat{t} = tU/L$, $\hat{\tau} = \tau/t_c$, $F_i = f_i/n_r$ and the parameter ϵ is $\epsilon = t_c \frac{U}{L}$ and can be interpreted as the Knudsen number.

The next step is to discretize this equation in space and time:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta \hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t})}{\Delta \hat{t}} + c_{ix} \frac{F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}} + \Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta \hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta \hat{t})}{\Delta \hat{x}} \\ + c_{iy} \frac{F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}} + \Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta \hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta \hat{t})}{\Delta \hat{y}} \\ + c_{iz} \frac{F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}} + \Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta \hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta \hat{t})}{\Delta \hat{z}} = \\ = \frac{1}{\hat{\tau} \epsilon} \left(F_i^{(eq)}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t}) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (1.69)$$

and now, by setting the lattice velocity \mathbf{c}_i as the lattice spacing divided by

the time step ($\mathbf{c}_i = \Delta\hat{\mathbf{x}}/\Delta\hat{t}$):

$$\frac{F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta\hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t})}{\Delta\hat{t}} + \frac{F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}} + \Delta\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta\hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta\hat{t})}{\Delta\hat{t}} = \frac{F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}} + \Delta\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t} + \Delta\hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t})}{\Delta\hat{t}} = \frac{1}{\hat{\tau}\epsilon} \left(F_i^{(eq)}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t}) - F_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{t}) \right). \quad (1.70)$$

Finally, by choosing $\Delta t = t_c$ and multiplying at both sides by $\Delta\hat{t}$ one finds the Lattice Boltzmann Equation:

$$\boxed{F_i(\mathbf{x} + \Delta\mathbf{x}, t + \Delta t) - F_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\tau} \left(F_i^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - F_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \right)}, \quad (1.71)$$

where the hats ($\hat{\quad}$) have been removed to simplify the notation. The LBE with BGK collision term is usually referred as LBGK.

In the following section some peculiarities and characteristics of this equation are going to be presented.

1.3.2 Some characteristics of the LBE

After the discretization from the BE to the LBE, one of the first questions that might arise is whether the LBE still verifies an H Theorem like the continuum BE did. Until now, the answer appears negative [60], there is no H functional that verifies the theorem at a global level, which is something that might cause numerical stability problems [50].

Another thing that should be noticed about the LBE is that all the physics is contained in the collision term. It is the term that makes the fluid evolve, and this is one of the main advantages of the lattice Boltzmann method, because new physics can be introduced just by changing or adding terms to the collision operator. In later sections, different ways to approximate the collision term will be presented.

One of the most important, if not the most, advantages of the LBE is that it is perfectly suited for parallelization [49], [60], [23], [37]. This comes from the fact that all the quantities involved are local and do not require any global operation [23], allowing the computational domain to be divided in several subdomains and computing each of them in a separate process. This represents a great advantage of the LBM over other CFD methods, seeing that modern computers tend to be more and more parallel. En example of the impressive parallel efficiency of the LBM can be seen in figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Example of the LBM parallel efficiency. Image taken from Ref. [37]

The lattice Boltzmann equation is the core of the lattice Boltzmann method, which is characterized by three main ingredients:

- The chosen lattice.
- The equilibrium functions $F_i^{(eq)}$.
- The approximation of the collision term.

A description of all these elements will be given in following sections.

1.3.3 2D and 3D lattices

The first ingredient of the LBM is the chosen lattice. They are all based on regular shapes (squares, hexagons, cubes) that can fill up all the space by repetition, and are characterized by the number of velocities that they allow, under the naming convention $DnQm$, where n is the number of dimensions and m is the number of possible velocities.

Not all possible lattices are valid though, a minimum of symmetry is required. For example, a simulation using the simple D2Q4 lattice (figure 1.3a) would not give a correct macroscopic solution because the directions of the particles are too limited. An hexagonal lattice like the D2Q7 is, however, symmetric enough and works well. There is no way of calculating “how much symmetry” is needed and all of this was found just by experience. Some examples of 2D and 3D lattices can be seen in figures 1.3 and 1.4.

Figure 1.3: Some examples of 2D lattices.

Figure 1.4: Some examples of 3D lattices.

One important remark about the LBM is that different lattices can be used in the same simulation, for example, one can be used to solve the Navier-Stokes equation and another one to solve the energy equation [30].

1.3.4 Equilibrium distributions and Galilean invariance

Local equilibrium distribution functions $f^{eq}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ play an essential role in the LBM, since they determine which macroscopic equations are going to be solved.

It was found in previous sections that the equilibrium distributions for the BE are Maxwell distributions (1.46). For solving the Navier-Stokes equations, a Taylor expansion of these distributions in terms of the microscopic velocity suffices. In particular, for the BGK case, the expansion is made up to second order in the Mach number ($Ma = \frac{u}{c_s}$), finding:

$$f_i^{eq} = \rho w_i \left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{c}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}}{c_s^2} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^2}{2c_s^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{c}_i \cdot \mathbf{u})^2}{2c_s^4} \right), \quad (1.72)$$

where the \mathbf{c}_i are the lattice velocities, $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are the local fluid density and velocity, c_s is the speed of sound of an ideal gas ($c_s^2 = RT$) and the w_i are weights (constants) for each lattice velocity that can be calculated by applying the conservation laws and isotropy [49].

One very nice property of this expansion is that its first three velocity moments are identical to the moments of the exact distribution function (the Maxwellian), making it equivalent in practical terms. However, since the expansion is only to order $O(\mathbf{u}^2)$, the fourth moment is no longer coincident with its Maxwellian equivalent and it is actually lacking a term $\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}$ [10]. This causes, when one tries to recover the macroscopic equations, the appearance of an extra term in the viscous momentum flux that leads to loss of Galilean invariance [41].

This a mayor problem, because any physical model should be Galilean invariant. However, the good thing is that this extra term is negligible when the Mach number is small ($Ma < 0.3$) [10], so the LBM with BGK approximation is still valid in the low Mach number, incompressible regime.

What all of this means, then, is that while the LBM is a compressible solver by construction, it is only able to produce good results in the case of incompressible flow, in the low Mach number limit.

This limitation could be theoretically solved by expanding the equilibrium function to higher orders, so that fourth and higher moments can be exactly recovered. The problem is that this needs more sophisticated and complex lattices that are able to keep the symmetry of higher rank tensors [52].

Attempts to develop a compressible LBM are numerous, for example, in Refs. [36], [31] and [38], LBMs able to solve the compressible Euler equations are presented.

1.3.5 Alternative approximations of the collision term

The BGK approximation

$$Q_i = \frac{1}{\tau} \left(F_i^{(eq)} - F_i \right) \quad (1.73)$$

is also known as a Single Relaxation Time (SRT) approach because all the different F_i are forced to have the same τ . This is a very simple scheme, and, as already mentioned, is very limited to the case of low Mach numbers.

To overcome or, at least, improve this limitation, Multiple Relaxation Time (MRT) schemes have been developed [11], with the collision term written as:

$$Q^{MRT} = M_{ij}^{-1} \hat{S}_{ij} (m_i^{eq} - m_i), \quad (1.74)$$

where the collision process is carried out in moment space instead of the usual velocity space. The collision matrix \hat{S}_{ij} is diagonal, m_i^{eq} is the equilibrium value of the moment m_i and M_{ij} is the transformation matrix.

Another alternative to the BGK approximation is the Entropic LBM (ELBM) scheme [3]. This is a SRT method which forces the verification of an H Theorem at a local level, improving the stability of the scheme. However, this method is computationally expensive and thus is not used on practical engineering applications [24].

Collision term used in XFlow:

As seen in Ref. [24], XFlow uses a modified MRT collision operator that is implemented in central moment space, unlike the standard MRT. This improves the Galilean invariance and the numerical stability for a given velocity set [40].

Raw moments can be defined as

$$\mu_{x^k y^l z^m} = \sum_i^N f_i c_{ix}^k c_{iy}^l c_{iz}^m, \quad (1.75)$$

where c_{ix} , c_{iy} and c_{iz} are the x , y and z components of the lattice velocities \mathbf{c}_i and k, l, m are integers. On the other side, central moments are

$$\hat{\mu}_{x^k y^l z^m} = \sum_i^N f_i (c_{ix} - u_x)^k (c_{iy} - u_y)^l (c_{iz} - u_z)^m. \quad (1.76)$$

1.3.6 Macroscopic variables, recovering Navier-Stokes

When running a simulation based on the LBM, one is not particularly interested in knowing the individual distribution functions, but rather on the macroscopic and measurable variables like density, velocity and pressure.

When dealing with the BE, it was seen that these quantities could be recovered as the velocity moments of the distribution functions (equations (1.49) to (1.51)). Now, in the discretized case, the integrals become sums and one has [52]:

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = m \sum_i f_i(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (1.77)$$

$$\rho \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = m \sum_i \mathbf{c}_i f_i(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (1.78)$$

$$\mathbf{\Pi} = m \sum_i \mathbf{c}_i \mathbf{c}_i f_i(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (1.79)$$

which define, respectively, the mass density, current density and momentum flux tensor of the fluid. The first two quantities ρ and $\rho \mathbf{u}$ are conserved,

however, it should be noted that only the trace of the momentum flux tensor is conserved [52], which corresponds to the fluid energy (pressure).

Just like with the continuous Boltzmann equation, the macroscopic equations that arise from the LBGK can be obtained by means of a Chapman-Enskog expansion. By doing this, and under the *assumption* of incompressible (low Mach) flow, the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations are recovered, with an *ideal* state equation

$$P(\rho) = \rho c_s^2, \quad (1.80)$$

and a kinematic viscosity

$$\nu = c_s^2 \left(\tau - \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right). \quad (1.81)$$

The process of recovering the Navier-Stokes equations from the LBGK is long and tedious, and is not the objective of this work to give a detailed description of it. The complete formulation and more information about it can be seen in multiple sources like [60], [49], [5] or [52].

1.3.7 Thermodynamic inconsistency

Another important aspect of the LBM that should be noted is that it is thermodynamically inconsistent.

A thermodynamically consistent model is one in which pressure, density and temperature are always related through the equation of state (1.80) at all times during the evolution of the fluid. But this is not feasible with just a subset of discrete microscopic velocities, like the LBM has.

To understand this, one has to remember that, in kinetic theory, the temperature of a fluid is related to the microscopic velocity of the particles, with zero temperature corresponding to no movement. The problem of the LBM is, then, that the microscopic velocities are limited to just the set of lattice velocities, so the range of temperatures that can be supported is restricted to the ones corresponding to the magnitudes of the lattice velocities [49].

What this means, for practical purposes, is that the great majority of lattice Boltzmann schemes are *isothermal* or *athermal* and, thus, only compute the density and velocity macroscopic fields, treating the temperature as a constant.

This important limitation has been a field of intense study, and alternative models have been developed in order to allow the simulation of thermal effects in LB schemes.

One of this models is presented in Ref. [20], where a second distribution function is introduced to model the temperature field. This means that two families of distribution functions are used: one for the velocity and density (f_i) and another for the temperature field (g_i). By doing so, two LBEs have to be solved:

- One equation for the f_i distribution functions and from which the macroscopic density and velocity will be calculated.
- A second equation for the g_i distribution functions, very similar to the LBGK equation and from which the macroscopic temperature is recovered as

$$T = \sum g_i. \quad (1.82)$$

Other approaches towards developing a thermal LBM can be seen in Refs. [34] (multi-speed approach) and [43] (passive scalar approach).

1.3.8 Boundary conditions

One of the advantages of the LBM that is most mentioned in the literature is how easy is to implement boundary conditions in complex geometries. This is, however, a very controversial claim. In words of D. A. Wolf in [60]:

“You often can find quotes like ‘difficult geometrical boundary conditions are readily handled’ in the introduction of an article only to find out that the authors performed some simulation over a square with periodic boundary conditions. Much more realistic is the remark of He et al. (1997) that ‘the real hydrodynamic boundary conditions have not been fully understood’.”

The truth relies probably somewhere in the middle: complex boundaries are easy to implement, but that does not mean that the results are going to be as accurate as with other CFD schemes. The problem of the LBM is that the lattice is very limited in shape (only cubes can be used in 3D) and, thus, it is difficult to adapt to curved shapes or lines that are not parallel to the cubic lattice. What happens when dealing with such shapes is that the boundaries are “staircased” in order to fit the requirements of the lattice. This can be seen

Figure 1.5: Complex geometries with different numerical schemes. The mesh used in Fluent can better adapt to the shape, while the LBM staircases the boundary. Image taken from Ref. [4].

in figure 1.5. The problem of this approach is that it introduces an artificial rugosity on the surface of order $1/L$ [49], where L is the typical linear size of the obstacle in lattice units, which may deteriorate the accuracy of the near-wall flow computation.

To overcome this limitation, various methods have been proposed. Some of them, instead of staircasing the geometry, handle the data transfer between the boundary and the lattice points by applying an appropriate interpolation, like in [22], [15] or [7], or a Taylor expansion like in [45]. Other methods consist on taking the LBE and, instead of solving it in a regular lattice like the LBM does, solve it by using other numerical techniques like finite volumes or finite elements, which allow more flexible meshes.

The problem of this methods is that they introduce more complexity into the numerical scheme, while the LBM is known for its simplicity and ease to parallelize. Therefore, some equilibrium has to be found between numerical accuracy and keeping the simplicity of the LBM.

In this section some implementations of boundary conditions in the LBM will be presented, but they are going to be limited to the ones that will be applied later in the simulations with XFlow. A review of many other BC can be seen in [27]. For simplicity a 2D lattice (D2Q9) will be used.

1.3.8.1 No-slip conditions

Boundary conditions can be applied in two cases: *On-Grid*, when the boundary is exactly in the nodes of the lattice, and *Mid-Grid*, when the boundary lies in the middle between two lines of nodes.

Figure 1.6: D2Q9 lattice with numbered velocities. [9]

No-slip conditions imply zero velocity at the boundaries. This means, from the LBM point of view, that the particles must “bounce-back” after they collide with the boundary. This can be seen in figure 1.7.

Figure 1.7: No-slip boundary conditions. After collision, the velocity of the particle is inverted. Pictures taken from [49].

In terms of distribution functions, these conditions are expressed, for the On-Grid case as

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_7(x, y) \\ f_4(x, y) \\ f_8(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_5 \\ f_2 \\ f_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.83)$$

and for the Mid-Grid case as

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_7(x, y) \\ f_4(x, y) \\ f_8(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_5(x-1, y-1) \\ f_2(x, y-1) \\ f_6(x+1, y-1) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1.84)$$

1.3.8.2 Free-slip conditions

Free-slip conditions are applied when the boundary has negligible friction and the fluid can have tangential velocity. In the LBM this means that particles

must be “reflected” after they collide with the boundary, as seen in figure (1.8).

Figure 1.8: Free-slip boundary conditions. The particles are “reflected” after collision. Pictures taken from [49].

Again, in terms of distribution functions this is written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_7 \\ f_4 \\ f_8 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_5 \\ f_2 \\ f_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.85)$$

for the On-Grid case, and as

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_7(x, y) \\ f_4(x, y) \\ f_8(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_5(x-1, y-1) \\ f_2(x, y-1) \\ f_6(x+1, y-1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.86)$$

for the Mid-Grid case.

1.3.8.3 LODI conditions

When solving a fluid flow, one has to pay special attention to the treatment of open boundaries, since the truncation of the space into a reduced domain should have the least possible effect on the solution.

The LODI (Locally One-Dimensional Inviscid) boundary conditions can be applied to open boundaries to estimate the far-field environment, avoiding the reflection of pressure waves and, thus, achieving a better solution overall.

This is done by solving the LODI equations (the Euler equations without the transverse terms) at the boundary, with the goal of finding an ideal value for the pressure and the velocity that can be applied as Dirichlet conditions, avoiding the reflections.

In 2D, for an open boundary normal to the x direction, the LODI equations are

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + u_x \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} + \rho \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (1.87)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t} + u_x \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (1.88)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial t} + u_x \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (1.89)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho E)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial[u_x(\rho E + p)]}{\partial x} = 0. \quad (1.90)$$

Writing this in vector form results in

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{\Gamma}_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (1.91)$$

from which the amplitude variations \mathbf{L} can be computed as $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{S} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{U}$, with \mathbf{S} being a matrix of left eigenvectors of $\mathbf{\Gamma}_x$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ de diagonal matrix of its eigenvalues. This way, the LODI equations can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{S}^{-1} \mathbf{L} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (1.92)$$

where the amplitude variations are

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{Bmatrix} L_1 \\ L_2 \\ L_3 \\ L_4 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} (u_x - c_s) \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} - \rho c_s \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} \right) \\ u_x \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \\ u_x \left(c_s^2 \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) \\ (u_x + c_s) \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \rho c_s \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} \right) \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (1.93)$$

allowing equations (1.87) to (1.90) to be written as

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2c_s^2} (L_4 + L_1) - \frac{1}{c_s^2} L_3 = 0, \quad (1.94)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2\rho c_s} (L_4 - L_1) = 0, \quad (1.95)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial t} + L_2 = 0, \quad (1.96)$$

in the isothermal case.

Figure 1.9: Boundary between two nodes. Outlet conditions will be applied at x_b . Picture taken from Ref. [42].

Implementation in an outlet:

Implementation of LODI boundary conditions in LBM is carefully presented in [42]. Here only a brief description will be made for the case of an outlet (the only case used in our XFlow simulations).

For a perpendicular outlet located mid-grid ($\delta q = 1/2$, check figure 1.9) where the reference pressure $p_b = p(x_b)$ is fixed, the pressure anti-bounce back boundary condition can be applied:

$$f_{\bar{\alpha}}(\mathbf{x}_f, t + 1) = -\tilde{f}_{\bar{\alpha}}(\mathbf{x}_f, t) + 2f_{\alpha}^{eq+}(\mathbf{x}_b, \hat{t}) + (2 - s_\nu)[f_{\alpha}^+(\mathbf{x}_f, t) - f_{\alpha}^{eq+}(\mathbf{x}_f, t)], \quad (1.97)$$

where the first term is the anti-bounce back, the second term is for the Dirichlet pressure and the last one is a correction to eliminate second-order error terms. The notation of the original article has been used, where $\tilde{f}_{\bar{\alpha}}$ are the post-collision distribution functions, $\bar{\alpha}$ is the opposite direction to α , f_{α}^{eq+} is the symmetric equilibrium function and s_ν is the relaxation time.

The f_{α}^{eq+} are calculated as

$$f_{\alpha}^{eq+} = \omega_\alpha \rho + \frac{9}{2} \omega_\alpha \rho_0 \left[(\mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{u})^2 - \frac{1}{3} (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{u}) \right], \quad (1.98)$$

where \mathbf{u} and $\rho = pc_s^{-2}$ are calculated from the LODI equations.

1.3.9 The LBM algorithm

To illustrate how the LBM algorithm works, the BGK scheme is going to be used. Under this approximation, the LBE can be written as

$$f_i(\mathbf{x} + \Delta \mathbf{x}, t + \Delta t) = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) + \frac{1}{\tau} \left(f_i^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \quad (1.99)$$

With this, the LBM algorithm goes as follows:

1. Initialization.

The equilibrium distributions f_i^{eq} are calculated from the initial conditions of the macroscopic fields ρ and \mathbf{u} :

$$f_i^{eq} = \rho w_i \left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{c}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}}{c_s^2} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^2}{2c_s^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{c}_i \cdot \mathbf{u})^2}{2c_s^4} \right), \quad (1.100)$$

and $f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is set as:

$$f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = f_i^{eq}(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (1.101)$$

2. Collision.

The collision step (right hand side of (1.99)) is calculated:

$$f_i'(\mathbf{x}, t) = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) + \frac{1}{\tau} \left(f_i^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \right). \quad (1.102)$$

3. Streaming.

The streaming step (left hand side of (1.99)) is now calculated:

$$f_i(\mathbf{x} + \Delta\mathbf{x}, t + \Delta t) = f_i'(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (1.103)$$

4. Calculation of macroscopic variables.

After the time step has been completed, the macroscopic variables are calculated again using equations (1.77)-(1.79). Then these functions can be used to calculate the new equilibrium distributions and the algorithm starts again in step 2.

The boundary conditions, depending on their type, can be applied at different stages of this algorithm. Some are imposed before the collision and streaming steps [39], some act on the collision step, and others come during or after the streaming step [63]. A review of many different BC can be seen in [27]. Judging from the consulted references, one would say that, generally, inlet and outlet conditions are imposed before collision and streaming, and bounce-back or free-slip conditions are applied after streaming to the distribution functions that have collided or “traspased” the walls.

1.3.10 Summary of the LBM.

As already seen, the Boltzmann equation, which describes microscopically the evolution of a rarefied gas, can recover at the macroscopic level the Navier-Stokes equations in low Knudsen number limit. The lattice Boltzmann equation is a simplification or discretization of the BE that can be summarized as follows:

After this simplification, the LBE is still able to recover the correct behavior at a macroscopic level, that is, the Navier-Stokes equations.

1.3.10.1 The LBM is not a rarefied gas approximation

One misconception that might arise after seeing how the LBE is obtained is to think that since the BE is only valid for rarefied media, then the LBE should also be only valid for this kind of fluid. This is totally false, cit-

ing S. Succi in [52], “*although kinetic theory is originally meant to describe weakly-interacting (dilute) systems, it can also be applied whenever strong interactions between elementary degrees of freedom can be cast in the form of weak interactions between appropriate **collective** degrees of freedom (quasi-particles)*”. This is exactly the case of the LBE, where these “quasi-particles” are the macromolecules that represent a large number of individual fluid particles.

Another mistake might be to think that the LBE is only valid for ideal gases, since it uses an ideal gas state equation (1.80), but this is again not correct. One has to remember that the LBM is only valid in low Mach, incompressible limit and, for incompressible flows the state equation does not play any role. This issue is also addressed in [52].

1.3.10.2 Advantages and drawbacks of the LBM

Some advantages and disadvantages of the LBM in comparison with the more classical CFD methods are outlined here:

- The equations that have to be solved are simpler than the discretization of Navier-Stokes.
- Thanks to the locality of the collision operator, the LBM is extremely well suited for parallel computing. Each lattice node can be computed separately.
- New physics can be easily added to the model by changing the collision term.
- No need to create a specific mesh for each geometry. A regular lattice is always used.
- Easy handling of complex geometries, but less accurate than with other CFD methods, due to the rigid lattice (This has improved a lot with the interpolated and Taylor expanded boundary conditions).
- Limited to low Mach numbers.
- Works for high Knudsen number applications, where the medium can not be modeled as a fluid and a macroscopic description like Navier-Stokes fails.

1.4 Application to Multiphase Problems

Apart from being a useful scheme for simulating the Navier-Stokes equations, the LBM can also be used to solve numerically other macroscopic models. For example, the phase separation of a binary mixture by means of the Cahn-Hilliard equation.

This is a case of special interest in this work because XFlow has recently incorporated a new LBM solver for multiphase problems based on the Cahn-Hilliard equation. The exact implementation is not known to us, but it is probably similar to what is going to be presented here.

1.4.1 The Cahn-Hilliard equation

This section will begin by describing the Cahn-Hilliard equation and the phenomena that it models. The theory presented here is based on Refs. [48] and [57].

Consider a homogeneous binary mixture of fluids A and B at a certain temperature T . The state of this system can be characterized by its temperature and concentration ϕ , defined as:

$$\phi = \frac{n_A - n_B}{n_A + n_B}, \quad (1.104)$$

so that $\phi \in [-1, 1]$. Here, n_A and n_B are the densities of the components in the fluid and $n_A + n_B$ is the mean density of the mixture.

The question that is going to be studied here is: what happens if the system is suddenly cooled down? Three different outcomes are possible. This can be seen in a (ϕ, T) diagram (figure 1.10).

If the mixture is cooled down to a temperature T_0 and (ϕ, T_0) is above the bold line, then no phase separation will occur and the mixture will remain homogeneous. On the other side, if it falls below the bold line, phase separation can appear in two different ways:

- Nucleation and growth: small “bubbles” where one of the two phases dominates will start to appear in the mixture.
- Spinodal decomposition: the two phases will start to separate into independent regions, which will become larger and larger over time.

The Cahn-Hilliard equation is only accurate to describe the case of spinodal decomposition. To deduce its expression let us first study why phase separation occurs.

Figure 1.10: ϕ - T diagram. Based on a picture from [57].

The Gibbs free energy of the mixture is given by

$$F = E - TS, \quad (1.105)$$

where E is the internal energy, T the temperature and S the entropy. Initially, when the fluid is suddenly cooled down, the free energy F is homogeneous and a new quantity $\nu(\phi)$ can be defined:

$$\nu(\phi) = \frac{F}{V}. \quad (1.106)$$

This is known as the *homogeneous free energy* (F per unit volume). For a given temperature, $\nu(\phi)$ can be approximated as

$$\nu(\phi) = \frac{A}{4}\phi^4 + \frac{B}{2}\phi^2, \quad (1.107)$$

where $A > 0$ and $B < 0$ are constants.

In figure 1.12 the homogeneous free energy is shown for a case where the temperature is lower than the critical temperature T_c . The points ϕ^+ , ϕ^- , ϕ_{s+} and ϕ_{s-} are the ones who define the different regions in figure 1.10.

When, at the moment of the cooling, the concentration ϕ is between ϕ^- and ϕ^+ , phase separation will occur because it is energetically favorable; the concentration *wants* to go towards the equilibrium values ϕ^- and ϕ^+ .

Figure 1.11: Spinodal decomposition (left) vs nucleation and growth (right). Picture taken from Ref. [17].

For the case of spinodal decomposition, after some time, there will be some regions in the mixture with concentration ϕ^+ and other regions with ϕ^- .

After the initial cooling, phase separation begins and the mixture is no longer homogeneous, which means that the identity (1.106) no longer holds and some correction is needed. The formation of separated domains implies the existence of interfaces where there is a very high gradient of concentration, and these gradients will also have some influence in the free energy of the mixture. Taking this into account, a first order correction to the homogeneous free energy can be

$$F(\phi) = \int \left(\nu(\phi) + \frac{k}{2} |\nabla\phi|^2 \right) dr. \quad (1.108)$$

And, from here, a chemical potential μ can be defined as the variation (functional derivative) of ν with respect to the concentration:

$$\mu = \frac{\delta F}{\delta\phi} = \frac{\partial I}{\partial\phi} - \frac{\partial}{\partial\mathbf{r}} \frac{\partial I}{\partial\nabla\phi} = \nu'(\phi) - \nabla \left(2\frac{k}{2} |\nabla\phi| \right) = \nu'(\phi) - k\nabla^2\phi, \quad (1.109)$$

where I is the integrand of (1.108).

On the other side, the evolution of the concentration ϕ is given by:

$$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} = \nabla (M(\phi)\nabla\mu). \quad (1.110)$$

This is the Cahn-Hilliard (C-H) equation, where $M(\phi)$ is called the mobility and controls the speed of the diffusion process and depends on how the

Figure 1.12: Homogeneous free energy. Based on a picture from [57].

concentration is in each point. However, this is difficult to implement in Lattice Boltzmann and therefore, in the present case, a constant value M_0 will be used. This allows the Cahn-Hilliard equation to be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = M_0 \nabla^2 \mu = -M_0 \nabla^2 (k \nabla^2 \phi - A \phi^3 - B \phi), \quad (1.111)$$

where the equations (1.107) and (1.110) were used in order to get the second identity.

1.4.2 Coupling the Cahn-Hilliard equation with Navier-Stokes

The Cahn-Hilliard equation (1.111) describes, then, the evolution of ϕ for a *static* mixture, but the objective is to be able to simulate a fluid in movement. For this, based on ref. [57], the velocity field has to be included in the Cahn-Hilliard equation by adding the boxed term:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \boxed{\mathbf{v} \nabla \phi} = M_0 \nabla^2 \mu = -M_0 \nabla^2 (k \nabla^2 \phi - A \phi^3 - B \phi). \quad (1.112)$$

The velocity field will be calculated separately using the Navier-Stokes equation.

By adding this term, the N-S equation has been linked to C-H, and now the opposite has to be done, because changes in the concentration field should also have some impact on the velocity field. This can be done in the following way:

- In the presence of a non uniform concentration, a thermodynamic force density $-\phi\nabla\mu$ appears at each point of the fluid. This means that the components of the mixture tend to separate (and, therefore, move) due to gradients of the chemical potential μ .
- This force density can be written as the divergence of a “chemical” pressure tensor:

$$\phi\nabla\mu = \nabla\mathbb{P}^{chem}. \quad (1.113)$$

By taking this into account, the incompressible Navier-Stokes equation can be written as

$$\rho[\mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{v}\nabla)\mathbf{v}] = \eta\nabla^2\mathbf{v} - \nabla\mathbb{P}^{th}, \quad (1.114)$$

where the thermodynamic pressure tensor is given by $\mathbb{P}^{th} = \mathbb{P} + \mathbb{P}^{chem}$, \mathbb{P} being the isotropic pressure tensor.

This way, the coupled system of equations can be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} + \boxed{\mathbf{v}\nabla\phi} = M_0\nabla^2\mu = -M_0\nabla^2(k\nabla^2\phi - A\phi^3 - B\phi), \quad (1.115)$$

$$\rho[\mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{v}\nabla)\mathbf{v}] = \eta\nabla^2\mathbf{v} - \boxed{\phi\nabla\mu} - \nabla\mathbb{P}. \quad (1.116)$$

1.4.3 A lattice Boltzmann model

This time two equations have to be solved, which means that two families of distribution functions are needed: f_i for the velocity and g_i for the concentration, where the index i goes from 1 to N , with N being the number of lattice velocities. The LBM presented here is the one presented in Ref. [57], based on the Cahn-Hilliard LBM introduced by Swift et al. in Ref. [53].

The distribution functions are defined to verify:

$$\sum_i f_i = \rho, \quad \sum_i g_i = \phi. \quad (1.117)$$

Furthermore, the momentum in the direction α can be found as

$$\rho v_\alpha = \sum_i f_i c_{i\alpha}, \quad (1.118)$$

and the full pressure tensor as

$$\mathbb{P}_{\alpha\beta} = \sum_i f_i c_{i\alpha} c_{i\beta}, \quad (1.119)$$

which includes not only $\mathbb{P}_{\alpha\beta}^{th}$ but also dissipative (viscous) contributions and a trivial “kinetic pressure” $\rho v_\alpha v_\beta$ which arises in any fluid moving at a constant velocity \mathbf{v} .

The evolution of the two distribution functions is given by the following LBEs:

$$f_i(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{c}_i, t + 1) - f_i(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{1}{\tau_1} (f_i(\mathbf{r}, t) - f_i^{eq}(\mathbf{r}, t)), \quad (1.120)$$

$$g_i(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{c}_i, t + 1) - g_i(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{1}{\tau_2} (g_i(\mathbf{r}, t) - g_i^{eq}(\mathbf{r}, t)). \quad (1.121)$$

These are the LBEs with BGK collision operator. This means that the relaxation time τ_1 for the first equation can be calculated from the fluid viscosity as

$$\tau_1 = \frac{6\eta + 1}{2}. \quad (1.122)$$

Furthermore, the relaxation time τ_2 for the equation of the concentration is chosen as 1, which implies that (1.121) reduces to

$$g_i(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{c}_i, t + 1) = g_i^{eq}(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (1.123)$$

This system of equations, together with the conditions (1.117) to (1.119), forces the equilibrium distribution functions to verify the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_i f_i^{eq} &= \rho, & \sum_i g_i^{eq} c_{i\alpha} &= \phi v_\alpha, \\ \sum_i g_i^{eq} &= \phi, & \sum_i f_i^{eq} c_{i\alpha} c_{i\beta} &= \mathbb{P}_{\alpha\beta}^{th} + \rho v_\alpha v_\beta, \\ \sum_i f_i^{eq} \cdot c_{i\alpha} &= \rho v_\alpha, & \sum_i g_i^{eq} c_{i\alpha} c_{i\beta} &= \bar{M} \mu \delta_{\alpha\beta}^{th} + \phi v_\alpha v_\beta, \end{aligned} \quad (1.124)$$

where $\bar{M} \Delta t (\tau_2 - 1/2) = M$, which implies that $\bar{M} = 2M$ in the present case.

On the other side, the equilibrium functions are given by

$$f_i^{eq} = \rho w_\nu \left(A_\nu + 3v_\alpha c_{i\alpha} + \frac{9}{2} v_\alpha v_\beta c_{i\alpha} c_{i\beta} - \frac{3}{2} v^2 + G_{\alpha\beta} c_{i\alpha} c_{i\beta} \right), \quad (1.125)$$

where the subindex ν stands for the possible speeds of the lattice. For example, for the lattice D3Q15, there are 15 possible velocities ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 14$) and 3 possible speeds ($\nu = 0, 1, \sqrt{3}$) and the constants in the equilibrium function are

$$\begin{aligned} w_0 &= \frac{2}{9}, & A_0 &= \frac{9}{2} - \frac{7}{2} \text{tr} \mathbb{P}^{th}, \\ w_1 &= \frac{1}{9}, & A_1 &= A_3 = \frac{1}{\rho} \text{tr} \mathbb{P}^{th}, \\ w_3 &= \frac{1}{72}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.126)$$

and the tensor $G_{\alpha\beta}$ is

$$G_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{9}{2\rho} \mathbb{P}_{\alpha\beta}^{th} - \frac{3\delta_{\alpha\beta}}{2\rho} \text{Tr} \mathbb{P}^{th}. \quad (1.127)$$

The equilibrium function g^{eq} is given by the same expression, just changing \mathbb{P}^{th} by $\bar{M}\mu\mathbb{I}$.

Finally, μ and \mathbb{P}^{th} are obtained from the Gibbs free energy, and read

$$\mu = A\phi^3 + B\phi + k\nabla^2\phi, \quad (1.128)$$

$$\mathbb{P}_{\alpha\beta}^{th} = \frac{\rho}{3}\delta_{\alpha\beta} + \mathbb{P}_{\alpha\beta}^{chem}. \quad (1.129)$$

This is the numerical model used to solve the coupled system (1.120),(1.123). The macroscopic equations can be recovered by expanding the equations to $O((\Delta t)^2)$ and using the identities (1.124) [14].

Chapter 2

XFlow

Now that the basic theory behind the LBM has been presented, it is appropriate to describe some of the essential features and characteristics of XFlow before showing the simulations that have been carried out.

2.1 The LBM in XFlow

XFlow offers 2D and 3D thermal LBM-based solvers for single phase, multiphase and free surface problems. However, not much is known to us about their actual implementation.

As described in [24] and in previous sections, it is known that, at least for single phase problems, a multiple relaxation time (MRT) collision term in central moment space is used (equations (1.74) and (1.76)), which improves the Galilean invariance and the numerical stability of the scheme [40].

For the multiphase case, the solver is probably based on the Cahn-Hilliard LBM described in section 1.4.3 from Ref. [53] or the more recent method presented in Ref. [62].

2.2 Meshless CFD

One of the main advantages that XFlow claims to have over other CFD codes is its meshless approach. Meshless, meshfree or particle based methods get their name from the fact that they do not need to divide the continuum domain into discrete elements (like the finite volumes or finite elements methods do), that is, they do not need a mesh in the usual sense. Instead, the physi-

cal space is discretized in particles that can freely move within the domain, with the approximate solution being solved in each of the particles. This approach avoids the need of spending considerable amounts of time creating a suitable mesh and has several other advantages like easier handling of complex geometries, deformations, moving parts, fractures and damage in the components, etc. [33]

The LBM is also a particle based method but, strictly speaking, it cannot be considered a purely meshfree method [33] since it requires a lattice: the particle distributions functions are forced to move in a limited set of directions and can only be at a discrete amount of positions.

Calling XFlow a meshless code doesn't mean, then, that there is no underlying grid. It means that one doesn't have to worry about creating a sophisticated mesh for each particular case and geometry, substantially reducing the time spent preparing the simulation.

Instead, as seen in the previous section, a regular cubic lattice will be automatically generated by the software. This grid can accommodate to complex geometries by reducing the element size near the boundaries (each cube can be divided in 8 smaller cubes), all of this controlled by the user with just a small set of parameters.

2.3 Lattice Generation

As stated in the paragraph above, the program will generate a cubic lattice in the computational domain. The user can control the resolution of the grid by setting the "resolved scale" parameter (in meters). Furthermore, XFlow allows two different refinement algorithms to better adapt the lattice to the characteristics of the simulation:

- Refinement near static walls

The user can choose a smaller resolved scale in the vicinity of the surface of static boundaries. XFlow will progressively reduce the resolution size by a factor of 2 until arriving to the desired resolved scale. This is due to the cubic nature of the lattice, so the resolved scale near a boundary should satisfy $\frac{x}{2^n}$, x being the general resolved scale and n a positive integer.

- Adaptive refinement

This algorithm allows the lattice to change dynamically while the simulation is running, adapting to moving parts and refining the resolved scale in the locations where more precision is required. For example, refining the wake generated by an aircraft.

2.4 Initial and Boundary Conditions

Initial conditions have to be imposed for the velocity, pressure and temperature fields, together with the concentration in the case of multicomponent fluids. These fields can be imposed by the user, loaded from a previous simulation or automatically calculated by the program.

About the boundary conditions, the usual inlet and outlet options are available (velocity, mass flow and gauge pressure inlet or outlet) and can be imposed as a constant, a function or loaded from an external file. For the wall boundary conditions XFlow has the following wall functions: No wall function (velocity is just set to 0 at the boundary), free-slip, enhanced wall function and non-equilibrium enhanced wall function.

The recommended option is usually the enhanced wall function, whose formulation is as follows [44]:

$$\frac{U}{u_c} = \frac{U_1 + U_2}{u_c} = \frac{u_\tau U_1}{u_c u_\tau} + \frac{u_p U_2}{u_c u_p} = \frac{\tau_w u_\tau}{\rho u_\tau^2 u_c} f_1 \left(y^+ \frac{u_\tau}{u_c} \right) + \frac{\frac{dp_w}{dx}}{\left| \frac{dp_w}{dx} \right|} \frac{u_p}{u_c} f_2 \left(u^+ \frac{u_p}{u_c} \right), \quad (2.1)$$

where

$$y^+ = \frac{u_c y}{\nu}, \quad (2.2)$$

$$u_c = u_\tau + u_p, \quad (2.3)$$

$$u_\tau = \sqrt{|\tau_w|/\rho}, \quad (2.4)$$

$$u_p = \left(\frac{\nu}{\rho} \left| \frac{dp_w}{dx} \right| \right)^{1/3}, \quad (2.5)$$

with y^+ being the normal distance from the wall, u_τ the skin friction velocity, τ_w the turbulent wall shear stress, $\frac{dp_w}{dx}$ the wall pressure gradient, u_c is a velocity scale defined from those two wall parameters and U the mean velocity at a given distance from the wall. This wall model is a generalized wall function made as a combination of the zero pressure gradient law f_1 and the zero wall stress function f_2 , which can be seen in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Enhanced Wall Basic Functions [44]

2.5 Turbulence Modeling

The mathematical model for the turbulence used in XFlow is the Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) approach. This means that the turbulence at scales bigger than the chosen resolution will be fully resolved, while subgrid scales have to be modeled.

The recommended model for the subgrid scales is the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy (WALE) [13], but the user can also choose a Smagorinsky, Dynamic Smagorinsky or Spalart-Allmaras model. Alternatively, it can be chosen not to solve the subgrid scales at all.

The WALE model can be summarized as follows:

$$\nu_{turbulent} = \Delta^2 \frac{(G_{\alpha\beta}^d G_{\alpha\beta}^d)^{3/2}}{(S_{\alpha\beta}^d S_{\alpha\beta}^d)^{5/2} + (G_{\alpha\beta}^d G_{\alpha\beta}^d)^{5/4}}, \quad (2.6)$$

where

$$S_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_\alpha}{\partial r_\beta} + \frac{\partial v_\beta}{\partial r_\alpha} \right), \quad (2.7)$$

$$G_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} (g_{\alpha\beta}^2 + g_{\beta\alpha}^2) - \frac{1}{3} \delta_{\alpha\beta} g_{\gamma\gamma}^2, \quad (2.8)$$

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\partial v_\alpha}{\partial r_\beta}, \quad (2.9)$$

$$\Delta = C_w \text{Vol}^{1/3}, \quad (2.10)$$

and the constant C_w in the cutoff length scale Δ has a recommended empiric value of 0.2 [55], although it can be changed by the user.

Figure 2.2: VOF example. Blue region corresponds to one fluid (VOF=0) and the red area corresponds to the other (VOF=1). There is an interface between the two fluids.

2.6 The Stability Parameter

One key quantity that is going to appear multiple times when discussing the numerical results is the stability parameter.

This is a parameter that is calculated by XFlow at each time step, and it gives an idea of the stability of the simulation. Values over 1 mean that CFL condition is not being satisfied at some point of the domain and, thus, indicates that a shorter time step should be selected.

In general it is recommended to have a stability parameter around the range 0.1-0.3 and, particularly, for the multiphase solver that is going to be used, the recommendation is to have a value between 0.05 and 0.1.

2.7 Interface Tracking in Multiphase Problems

In cases where there are two different fluids, XFlow needs to keep track of where each phase is. To do so, it uses a method called Volume of Fluid (VOF) or volume of liquid phase, which assigns a value of 0 to one fluid and 1 to the other.

In places where the two phases are not completely separated the value will be between 0 and 1, and the regions with high gradient are interpreted as interfaces. An example can be seen in figure 2.2.

Chapter 3

Validation Tests

This chapter is devoted to the main objective of this work: the validation tests with XFlow.

As already explained, three different cases have been studied: one thermal and two multiphase problems. The first case corresponds to the T-Junction benchmark, and has been performed with a three-dimensional, single phase, thermal solver. On the other side, the rising bubble and Rayleigh-Taylor instability problems have been solved using a two-dimensional, multiphase, isothermal solver.

It should be noted that XFlow has two multiphase solvers: one of them is older and is already validated for some kind of problems, while the other is very recent and still in development. The one studied here is the latter.

In general, due to their higher computational cost, the 3D simulations of the T-Junction have been carried out at the CESGA cluster in an MPI environment. On the other side, many of the computations for the multiphase problems have been executed in a regular PC, with only a few more demanding cases being sent to the cluster.

3.1 T-Junction Benchmark

In 2009, the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) proposed an international benchmarking exercise to test the ability of the then state-of-the-art CFD codes to predict important parameters affecting high-cycle thermal fatigue in mixing tees, a test formally known as the “OECD/NEA-Vattenfall T-junction Benchmark exercise”. The fatigue effects in this kind of junctions became a big safety concern after one incident in a French nuclear power

Figure 3.1: Detail of mixing area.

plant, where cracks appeared in junctions where cold and hot streams of water were mixing. [47] [46]

The cause of this fractures is believed to be the permanent temperature fluctuation at the walls of the mixing area, due to the turbulent nature of the mixture. Therefore, it is very important that the simulation will correctly reproduce the mixing and the temperature fluctuations on the walls.

To compare and validate the numerical results of each simulation, measurements were made in an experimental setup in Sweden by Vattenfall Research and Development. These measurements include velocity profiles and temperatures at various points of the pipe. However, the benchmark was originally intended as a blind test, so the experimental measurements were not published until the numerical results were presented, and only the necessary boundary conditions, materials, geometry and other parameters were given to the participants.

In the present case, the same simulation is going to be performed with XFlow, comparing the numerical results with the experimental data and using this benchmark as a validation test for the code.

3.1.1 Description of the setup and available data

In this section, the necessary parameters to set up the simulation are given, together with a description of the experimental data available.

3.1.1.1 Geometrical data

The experimental setup can be seen in figure 3.2. There is a hot inlet (InHo) from the top and one cold inlet (InCo) from the left, in both cases the liquid being water. The two incoming pipes have a so-called stagnation chamber, whose mission is to obtain a very good quality, non turbulent, flow. The

Figure 3.2: Geometry T-Junction. Experimental setup [46]

Figure 3.3: Detail of the mixing zone.

inner diameter of the hot, vertical pipe, is $D_1 = 100\text{mm}$, while the horizontal pipe has a constant diameter $D_2 = 140\text{mm}$.

The stagnation chamber in the horizontal pipe is 80 diameters away from the tee junction, allowing the flow to be fully developed by the time it arrives to the mixing area. In the vertical pipe, however, fully developed flow cannot be expected since the stagnation chamber is only 20 diameters upstream the mixing area.

Inlet	Temperature (°C)	Pipe diameter (mm)	Measuring location (mm)	Volumetric flow rate (l/s)
Main(InCo)	19	140(D_2)	-420($3D_2$)	9.0
Branch(InHo)	36	100(D_1)	-310($3.1D_1$)	6.0

Table 3.1: Inlet measurements for temperature and flow rate.

3.1.1.2 Inlet boundary conditions

Measurements of the volumetric flow rate and temperature have been measured $3.1D_1$ and $3D_2$ upstream the hot and cold pipes respectively. This is represented in figure 3.3 with the two perpendicular lines at the inlets. The measured values are shown in table 3.1.

Apart from the flow rates, velocity profiles were also measured at the same locations, in the two perpendicular directions (x and y for InHo, y and z for InCo). There is data for the mean velocity profiles, the RMS velocity and the higher moments: skewness and flatness. However, only the mean velocity, defined as

$$U = \bar{u} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n u_i, \quad (3.1)$$

can be used as boundary condition.

For the hot inlet (InHo), the velocity profiles have been measured twice: first with cold water (same temperature as InCo) and then with hot water. The reason for doing this is that they had problems measuring the profiles in non-isothermal conditions, because changes in the refractive index due to temperature differences were affecting the laser measurements. As a consequence, the cold, isothermal, measurements are expected to be more accurate. Profiles for both inlets can be seen in figures 3.4 and 3.5.

It should be noted that the streamwise mean velocity (U) profiles have been scaled with the fluids' bulk velocity, U_{bulk} , at each inlet. The values of the bulk velocities are not given, but can be calculated from the volumetric flow rate, C , and the area of the pipe section, S , as

$$U_{bulk} = \frac{C}{S}, \quad (3.2)$$

giving the following values for each inlet:

$$U_{bulk}^h = \frac{C_h}{S_h} = \frac{C_h}{\pi(d_h/2)^2} = \frac{0.006 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}}{\pi \cdot 0.05^2 \text{ m}^2} \approx 0.76 \text{ m/s} \quad (3.3)$$

$$U_{bulk}^c = \frac{C_c}{S_c} = \frac{C_c}{\pi(d_c/2)^2} = \frac{0.009 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}}{\pi \cdot 0.07^2 \text{ m}^2} \approx 0.58 \text{ m/s} \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.4: Cold inlet velocity profiles measured along the z and y centerlines.

Figure 3.5: Hot inlet velocity profiles measured along the y and x centerlines.

It can be seen in figures 3.4 and 3.5 how the cold inlet has a fully developed flow, while in the hot inlet the shape is much more flat.

3.1.1.3 Downstream measurements

Apart from upstream measurements for velocity and temperature, downstream data was also gathered. These measurements consist in temperature and velocity profiles, taken at various sections in the outlet pipe. The purpose of this data is to have some reference experimental values that can be used to validate the results produced by XFlow.

The temperature measurements were taken with thermocouples of 0.13 mm diameter, placed approximately 1 mm from the inner pipe wall at locations $2D_2$, $4D_2$, $6D_2$, $8D_2$, $10D_2$, $15D_2$ and $20D_2$, as seen in figure 3.6. In each of these locations there were 4 thermocouples: one on the top, one on the bottom, one on the left and one on the right of the pipe, except at $15D_2$ and $20D_2$, where only top and bottom measurements were taken. Considering 0° as the top position and counting in counterclockwise direction, the placement of the thermocouples is defined as:

Location on x axis	Angular positions (degrees)
$2D_2$	0,90,180,270
$4D_2$	0,90,180,270
$6D_2$	0,90,180,270
$8D_2$	0,90,180,270
$10D_2$	0,90,180,270
$15D_2$	0,180
$20D_2$	0,180

Figure 3.6: Thermocouple locations along the T-Junction. Image taken from [46].

The data collected is an average at each position over a period of 300 seconds, and has been normalized and nondimensionalized by using the formula

$$T^* = \frac{T - T_{min}}{T_{max} - T_{min}}, \quad (3.5)$$

where $T_{max} = 36^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_{min} = 19^\circ\text{C}$, which are the hot and cold inlet temperatures. The measured profiles can be seen in figure 3.7. It should be noted that at some points there was no reported data, the reasons behind this are unknown to us.

Figure 3.7: Temperature experimental profiles.

Continuing with the downstream data, velocity profiles have been measured at positions $1.6D_2$, $2.6D_2$, $3.6D_2$ and $4.6D_2$. Like their upstream counterparts, they have been scaled with the bulk velocity of the fluid, which in this case is

$$U_{bulk} = \frac{C}{S} = \frac{C}{\pi(d/2)^2} = \frac{0.015m^3/s}{\pi \cdot 0.07^2m^2} \approx 0.97m/s. \quad (3.6)$$

These measurements include the three components of the velocity, giving a total of 12 profiles. They will be presented in the last section, compared with the numerical results of XFlow.

Finally, aside from averaged velocity and temperature profiles, transient data is also available. In particular, for some of the thermocouples between

Figure 3.8: Frequency of temperature oscillations. a clear peak appears at around 3.5 Hz. Image taken from [47].

$2D_2$ and $8D_2$ there are instantaneous temperature measurements over a period of 300 s taken with a frequency of 200 Hz.

This data is very important to study the thermal fatigue on the pipe, because the cracks on the walls are caused by the continuous temperature fluctuations in the mixing area. In fact, Fourier analysis of the transient data shows a peak between 3 and 4 Hz, as seen in figure 3.8, and it will be a challenge for XFlow to reproduce this behavior.

3.1.2 Simulation setup

Now that an overview of the problem has been presented, a description of how the simulation was performed can be made. A total of three different cases will be studied, each of them with a different mesh resolution, to see how the convergence of the numerical solution is.

3.1.2.1 3D geometry

The 3D geometry used in the simulation is the same as the one described in Ref. [28], and can be seen in figure 3.9. The inlets are placed where the experimental measurements were made, that is, $3.1D_1 = 310\text{mm}$ and $3D_2 = 420\text{mm}$ away from the origin. On the other side, the outlet is placed $22D_2 = 3080\text{mm}$ downstream.

Figure 3.9: 3D Geometry

Density (kg/m ³)	Dynamic viscosity (Ns/m ²)	Specific heat capacity (J/kgK)	Thermal Conductiv- ity (W/mK)	Expansion Coefficient (K ⁻¹)
997.0	$0.855 \cdot 10^{-3}$	4179	0.613	$0.276 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 3.2: Water properties at 300K. Data taken from Ref. [26].

3.1.2.2 Material properties

The materials involved in this simulation are, basically, the inner fluid and the pipe wall, which are water and Plexiglas respectively. For the water properties it was considered that the operating temperature was 300K (average between inlets), corresponding to the values found in table 3.2.

However, for the water viscosity the following model is used:

$$\mu(T) = 2.414 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot 10^{\frac{247.8}{T-140}}, \quad (3.7)$$

where T has units of Kelvin. This empiric formula was taken from Ref. [2] and is valid with an accuracy of 2.5% in the range of temperatures from 0°C to 370°C.

On the other side, the thermal properties of Plexiglas are listed in table 3.3.

Density (kg/m ³)	Specific heat capacity (J/kgK)	Thermal Con- ductivity (W/mK)	Expansion Coef- ficient (K ⁻¹)
1200.0	1460	0.190	$0.240 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 3.3: Thermal properties of Plexiglas. Data taken from Ref. [47].

3.1.2.3 Simulation environment

For this simulation a 3D thermal, single phase solver is going to be used. Radiation effects can be neglected since there are no external warm bodies and the temperature of the fluid is not particularly high.

The Reynolds number in this problem can be estimated as $Re \sim 1.6 \cdot 10^5$ based on the flow conditions downstream of the T-Junction ($D = 0.14$ m, $U_{bulk} = 0.97$ m/s) and using the water properties at 300 K. Because of this, a turbulence model is necessary.

Looking at the results obtained in previous simulations of this benchmark, it can be seen that the best results were obtained by the groups who used a LES model for the turbulence [47], which is precisely the turbulence model implemented in XFlow. LES is therefore used to compute the large eddies, while the subgrid scale has to be modeled. For this, the WALE model explained in section 2.5 was applied in the present simulation.

Apart from this, the system is subject to an external acceleration of -9.8 m/s in the z direction to account for the gravity.

3.1.2.4 Initial conditions

Basically, the chosen initial conditions are the following: the inner fluid is at rest ($\mathbf{v} = 0$) with a temperature of 300.65 K.

The temperature was chosen like this because it is the main value between the hot ($T_{InHo} = 309.15$ K) and the cold ($T_{InCo} = 292.15$ K) inlets. On the other side, the choice for the velocities requires a more detailed explanation.

If the pipe had only one inlet, the natural choice for the initial velocity field would be to have same value as the inlet velocity. However, since in this case the pipe has two perpendicular inlets, the choice of the most adequate initial conditions is more complicated. Different approaches were tested:

1. Initializing the horizontal pipe with the velocity profile of the cold inlet

and the vertical pipe with the velocity of the hot inlet.

This caused a numerical discontinuity in the mixing area, where two completely perpendicular flows were colliding at $t = 0$. As a consequence, pressure waves were generated within the domain and caused fluctuations in the velocity field.

2. Initializing with the velocity field from a previous computation.

This approach looked promising: make a first simulation with the initial conditions described above, wait until the solution is stable enough, and then use the final results as the initial conditions for the following “real” simulation.

However, this method had one problem: due to a bug in the current version of XFlow, the temperature field from the previous computation could not be used to initialize the simulation, so even if the velocity field was already developed, one still had to wait 4-5 seconds of computation until the temperature was correctly distributed.

3. Initializing with the fluid at rest.

Having all the fluid at rest avoided the formation of pressure waves inside the pipe. However, having zero velocity in the interior and a non-zero velocity profile at the inlets would also cause a discontinuity. To avoid this, the boundary conditions had to be modified as described in the next section.

With these conditions, the simulation needs 6-9 seconds to be perfectly initialized. Even if this is a longer time than with the previous method, having no need to perform a previous computation made this approach more attractive.

3.1.2.5 Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions for inlets, outlet and pipe wall are the following:

- Cold inlet
 - Temperature = 292.15 K.
 - Turbulence = 0%. The inlet flow, as described in [47], was of very good quality, and turbulence effects can be neglected.

- Velocity: the profile measured along the y direction (red points in figure 3.4.). Also, due to the axial symmetry of the profile, only the left one half is needed. The left part was chosen because it has more data points near the wall.

It should be noted that the volumetric flow produced by this profile was of 8.55 l/s, less than the 9 l/s measured by the flowmeter, as seen in table 3.1. This was already expected because in the documentation [47] is said that there was around a 5% discrepancy between the flow rate obtained from the velocity profiles and the one measured by the flowmeters.

In order to correct this, a constant velocity of 0.029 m/s was added to the profile. This is explained in appendix A.

Minimizing pressure waves and numerical discontinuities:

Since the inner fluid is initially at rest, directly imposing the velocity profiles would cause a discontinuity at the inlets, generating pressure waves in the domain that would affect the solution.

In order to minimize this, the velocity at the inlets has been smoothed in time during the first 4 seconds of simulation by multiplying it with a cosine function:

$$v(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1-\cos(\pi t/4)}{2} v_{profile} & t \leq 4 \text{ s} \\ v_{profile} & t > 4 \text{ s} \end{cases} \quad (3.8)$$

By doing this, we get a smoothly growing function during the first 4 seconds that does not cause discontinuities and greatly minimizes the pressure waves formed at the inlets. A graph of this modified velocity is shown in figure 3.10.

- Hot inlet

- Temperature = 309.15 K.
- Turbulence = 0%. Same reason as for the cold inlet.
- Velocity: the selected profile was the one measured along the y direction in non-isothermal conditions (black points in figure 3.5b.), because it has more data points near the wall. Again, only the left half was used.

A velocity correction for this profile was also needed. In this case it was necessary to add 0.04 m/s.

Figure 3.10: Smoothed inlet velocity.

The same smoothing during the first 4 seconds was applied too.

- Outlet

- Pressure outlet with 0 Gauge pressure.
- Adiabatic outlet.
- LODI conditions were applied to absorb any pressure waves generated at the inlets. The default relaxation time of 0.5 was used.

- Pipe walls

- No-slip boundary condition with enhanced wall function.
- Heat flux condition:

$$\text{Heat flux} = 13.6(288.15 - u(x, y, z)) \text{ W/m}^2, \quad (3.9)$$

where $u(x, y, z)$ is the temperature field inside the pipe, 288.15 K is the environmental temperature and 13.6 is the value of the Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC) for Plexiglas, as defined in appendix B.

Even though Plexiglas is not a very conducting material, a heat flux to the outside is still defined because it helps to lower the internal temperature (which XFlow tends to overestimate, as it will be seen in the following section).

3.1.2.6 Simulation parameters

- Time step

The time step is automatically calculated by XFlow using a set of parameters like a reference velocity, length and area, the Courant number and the lattice resolution. In this case:

- Reference velocity = 1 m/s, since this is approximately the bulk flow velocity.
- Reference length = 3.5 m.
- Reference area = front area (x direction).
- Courant = 1.

As for the lattices, three different cases were simulated.

- Lattice resolution

Different refinement degrees were used:

1. A coarse lattice with a resolution of 4 mm, leading to a total of 867,866 elements.
2. A more refined lattice with a resolution of 2 mm, which implies a total of 6,948,291 elements.
3. Finally, the objective was to run a computation with a lattice of just 1 mm resolution, but this led to a computation time much longer than the 24h limit of CESGA. To avoid this, only a rectangular region around the mixing area was refined to 1 mm, while the rest of the domain was resolved with a 4 mm scale. This gave a total of 15,790,630 elements. A detail of the domain and the refined volume can be seen in figure 3.11.

- Simulation time

For lattices 1 and 2, the simulation was run for 16 seconds, while for the more refined case only 10 seconds could be computed because of limited computation time.

Again, for the first two cases, the averaging for the temperature and a velocity fields was started at 9 s, for a total of 7 s of averaged data.

Figure 3.11: Detail of the refined domain. The volume inside the red rectangle is solved with a resolution of 1 mm, while the rest of the domain has a resolution of 4 mm.

Longer averaging times were tested but no significant improvements were noticed.

The reason for choosing 9 seconds as the starting time for averaging was that it was the instant when the pressure field was completely stabilized. This was a conservative approach because the temperature and velocity fields were probably of good quality already some seconds before.

For the more refined case, since only 10 s of simulation could be computed, the averaging was started at $t = 5$ s. In order to have the temperature and velocity fields ready in just 5 seconds, it was decided to **use a previous simulation as initial conditions**, only for this case. The previous simulation used to initialize the calculus was the one with a 4 mm resolution. Apart from this, **the reference velocity was lowered to 0.9 m/s** to slightly reduce the time step and allow the computation to finish in less than 24 hours.

With all the necessary information already presented, the numerical results can be finally shown.

3.1.3 Numerical results

The first thing to comment about the simulations is that the stability parameter was around 0.3 for the first two computations, while for the more refined mesh the value was around 0.4. A general look at the solutions is presented below.

Figure 3.12: T-Junction: instantaneous temperature field at $t = 16$ s for the case solved with a resolution of 2 mm.

Figure 3.13: T-Junction: averaged temperature field at $t = 16$ s for the case solved with a resolution of 2 mm.

3.1.3.1 Overview of the solution in the whole domain

The instantaneous and averaged temperature fields at $t = 16$ s can be seen in figures 3.12 and 3.13, which are taken from the simulation with a 2 mm lattice. In general it looks like a good solution and in line with the results obtained by other groups like Ref. [28].

A more detailed view of the mixing area can be seen in 3.14, where the solution with the finest mesh is displayed.

One interesting thing to note about the simulation with the finest lattice is that there were some errors in the temperature field. Looking at figure 3.15 it can be seen how there is a region in the interface between the cold and hot streams that is actually **colder than the inlet flow**. This is something that has no physical sense and might be caused by the higher stability parameter of this computation. This is not visible in figure 3.14 because the temperature scale has been limited to a minimum value of 292.15 K (the temperature of the cold inlet).

Figure 3.14: T-Junction: detail of instantaneous temperature field at $t = 16$ s for the computation with the finest mesh.

Figure 3.15: T-Junction: detail of errors in the temperature field when solving with the most refined lattice. It can be seen how there are darker blue spots in the interface. The temperature of these regions is around 2 degrees lesser than the cold inlet.

3.1.3.2 Temperature profiles and fluctuations

This is the first test of the benchmark in which the computational results can be compared against experimental data.

Before presenting the results, it is worth mentioning a very curious behavior that was observed in XFlow: **different temperature profiles were obtained when running identical simulations**, i.e., computing the same simulation two times gave results that were not identical. This implies the presence of some stochastic process in the thermal solver. To give a number, differences of ± 0.3 K were observed.

After commenting this issue, the final results can be presented:

Figure 3.16: T-Junction: temperature profiles obtained with the three computations compared with the experimental measurements.

From this graphs it is not clear whether refining the lattice actually improves the solution, because the best case, overall, seems to be the simulation

with a resolution of 2 mm.

The most tricky profile seems to be the one at 0° , which corresponds to the top of the pipe. All the simulations tend to overestimate the temperature, especially in the region close to the mixing area. This was something that was also observed, although not as severe, in all the simulations presented in [47], so it is not unique to XFlow.

The rest of the profiles look very good, especially for the simulation with 2 mm.

The other test for the thermal solver is to check its ability to predict a peak in the temperature fluctuations that was experimentally measured to be around 3.5 Hz.

In order to save the necessary transient data to perform a Fourier analysis, it was necessary to put a sensor inside the computational domain. The problem was that, due to a bug in XFlow, these sensors do not work in parallel computations, so we were limited to a serial simulation with a lattice resolution of just 4 mm (finer meshes exceeded the computational time limit). The simulation was run for a total of 20 seconds, but only the data from the last 15 has been used to study the temperature fluctuations. The results obtained with XFlow are compared against the experimental data in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.17: T-Junction: Fourier analysis of temperature fluctuations. The transient data was taken from the thermocouple located at $x = 2D$ and 270° and from a sensor in XFlow located in the exact same position.

The displayed data, which is from the sensor located at $x = 2D$ in the right side of the pipe (270°), seems to agree very well with the experimental measurements. Although the maximum is not as clear, it is very close to the experimental peak.

The results would have probably improved if the data could have been collected for a longer time (only 15 s of computational data vs 300 s of experimental measurements).

3.1.3.3 Velocity profiles

Finally, the velocity profiles obtained with XFlow at locations $x = 1.6D$, $x = 2.6D$, $x = 3.6D$ and $x = 4.6D$ can also be compared against their experimental counterparts.

Figure 3.18: x component of the velocity measured along the y axis in different downstream locations. Data taken from the 2 mm simulation.

(d) $x = 4.6D$

Figure 3.19: x component of the velocity measured along the z axis in different downstream locations. Data taken from the 2 mm simulation.

The data displayed in figures 3.18 and 3.19 is from the simulation with a 2 mm resolution, and corresponds to the profiles of the streamwise (x component) velocity, measured along the y and z directions, respectively. The results from XFlow agree very well with the experimental data.

3.1.4 Conclusions

In this section the T-Junction benchmark exercise was presented and the results obtained with XFlow have been compared with the available experimental data.

Overall, the performance of XFlow has been very good, even though some problems have been observed:

- Identical simulations lead to slightly different results, implying the existence of some stochastic process in the thermal solver.
- The solution with the finest lattice has predicted regions where the temperature is less than that of the cold inlet (figure 3.15), which is something that has no physical sense. Furthermore, it has given worst results than the simulation with a coarser mesh of 2 mm, as seen in figure 3.16. Both of these problems might be caused by the stability parameter, which has been higher in these simulations as compared with the others (~ 0.4 vs ~ 0.3).
- All the simulations overestimate the temperature near the mixing area for the profile at 0° . This was already observed in all the computations presented in [47], but it is more prominent in XFlow.

3.2 Rising Bubble

The first test for the multiphase solver is going to be the simulation of a rising bubble. This benchmark is a two phase problem where a bubble made of a certain fluid is surrounded by a more dense environment, causing it to rise under the gravitational acceleration. Two different cases will be tested, each of which with a different density and viscosity ratio between the fluids.

This problem was initially proposed by Hysing et al. in [25], where a detailed description of the setup and benchmark quantities are presented. Furthermore, the numerical results of three different groups that performed the benchmark are also given and will be used to compare with the simulations carried out in XFlow.

3.2.1 Case description

The geometry and initial configuration of the problem can be seen in figure 3.20. The bubble is initially circular with a radius $r_0 = 0.25$ and centered at $[0.5, 0.5]$ in a $[1 \times 2]$ rectangular domain. In the vertical walls a free-slip boundary condition is imposed, while at the top and bottom horizontal walls the condition will be no-slip.

Figure 3.20: Initial configuration. Picture from [25]

This type of problem is characterized by two dimensionless numbers: the

Eötvös and the Reynolds number, which are defined in [25] as follows:

$$Re = \frac{\rho_1 \sqrt{g}(2r_0)^{3/2}}{\mu_1}, \quad Eo = \frac{4\rho_1 g r_0^2}{\sigma}, \quad (3.10)$$

where ρ_1 and μ_1 are the density and viscosity of the heavier fluid, g is the gravitational acceleration, r_0 is the initial radius of the bubble and σ is the surface tension between the two fluids.

Experimental studies by Clift et al. [8] show that these two parameters are enough to predict the shape that the bubble will acquire as it ascends through the fluid, as seen in figure 3.21.

Figure 3.21: Diagram of shape regimes for bubbles and drops for different Reynolds and Eötvös numbers, taken from the book of Clift et al. [8].

In this benchmark two test cases are going to be computed, each of them corresponding to a bubble in a different regime. The first one is going to be a case where $Re = 35$ and $EO = 10$, which should give an ellipsoidal bubble; the second one will have a higher viscosity and density ratio, leading to $Re = 35$ and $EO = 125$, which should correspond to a bubble in the ellipsoidal-cap regime.

The physical properties of the fluids in both cases can be seen in the following table:

Test Case	ρ_1	ρ_2	μ_1	μ_2	g	σ	Re	EO	ρ_1/ρ_2	μ_1/μ_2
1	1000	100	10	1	0.98	24.5	35	10	10	10
2	1000	1	10	0.1	0.98	1.96	35	125	1000	100

Table 3.4: Physical parameters and dimensionless numbers for the two test cases.

3.2.2 Benchmark quantities

To properly analyze the performance of a given simulation, Hysing et al. [25] proposed the following benchmark quantities:

- **Center of mass position.** Since the bubble will deform during its ascent, it is necessary to define a point to track its position. In this case, the center of mass is used, which is defined as

$$\mathbf{X}_c = (x_c, y_c) = \frac{\int_{\Omega_2} \mathbf{x} dx}{\int_{\Omega_2} 1 dx}, \quad (3.11)$$

where Ω_2 is the region occupied by the bubble.

- **Circularity.** The degree of circularity is defined as the ratio between the perimeter of a circle with the same area as the bubble and the perimeter of the bubble. That is:

$$\phi = \frac{P_a}{P_b} = \frac{\text{perimeter of area-equivalent circle}}{\text{perimeter of bubble}} = \frac{\pi d_a}{P_b}. \quad (3.12)$$

If the area of the bubble is assumed to remain constant during its ascent, then P_a will just be the perimeter of the bubble at $t = 0$, when it was circular. For a perfectly circular bubble, ϕ is obviously 1.

Figure 3.22: Rising bubble, test case 1: shape of the bubble at $t = 3s$ as obtained by the three different groups in [25].

- **Rise velocity.** The mean velocity of the bubble is defined as

$$U_c = \frac{\int_{\Omega_2} \mathbf{u} dx}{\int_{\Omega_2} 1 dx}, \quad (3.13)$$

and, in particular, the velocity component opposite to the direction of gravity is called *rise velocity*, V_c .

All of these quantities will be computed for each case and compared with the previous results presented in [25].

3.2.3 Test case 1

As seen in table 3.4, this first case corresponds to a density and viscosity ratio of 10, $Re = 35$ and $EO = 10$, a configuration which should give an ellipsoidal bubble. The final shape of the bubble at $t = 3$ as obtained in [25] can be seen in figure 3.22.

3.2.3.1 Simulation setup

To carry out the computation in XFlow, the multiphase solver needs some other parameters apart from the physical properties of the fluids: the interface thickness and the mobility.

- **Interface thickness.** This parameter represents the number of lattice elements used to model the interface between the two fluids. The default value is 3, but several values between 1 and 5 were tested, as seen in figure 3.23.

Figure 3.23: Rising bubble, test case 1: interface thickness comparison at $t = 3$. All computations were made with the default mobility (0.02) and with a lattice resolution of $1/160$.

Looking at the results, the first thing that stands out is that none of the computations managed to correctly reproduce the shape of the bubble at $t = 3$, as the two filaments that appear at both sides of the bubble should not be there. Furthermore, the cases with an interface thickness of 1 and 1.5 also failed to give the correct position of the bubble. On the other side, by using $I = 3$ or $I = 5$, the solver correctly predicts that the top of the bubble will be at $y = 1.3$, as it should be by looking at figure 3.22.

Since the simulations with $I = 3$ and $I = 5$ provide roughly the same solution, the final selected value for the interface thickness was 3, because making it thicker does not provide any significant advantage.

- **Mobility.** This is a constant in the Cahn-Hilliard equation (1.111) that controls the diffusion between the two phases. The recommended value in XFlow is 0.02, but other values between 0.001 and 0.06 were tested and are compared in figure 3.24. Values over 0.06 led to unstable simulations.

The presented results show that increasing the mobility helps to reduce the size of the filaments, thus making the bubble more similar in shape to the correct one. Because of this, the selected value for the mobility was 0.06.

Figure 3.24: Rising bubble, test case 1: mobility comparison at $t = 3$. All computations were made with an interface thickness of 3 and with a lattice resolution of $1/160$.

However, seeing that changes in these parameters were not significantly helping to achieve a better solution, it was decided to do another test, namely, reduce the time step and see what happens.

The time step is automatically calculated by XFlow by taking into account the lattice resolution, a reference velocity, a reference area and the Courant number (by default $C = 1$). In this simulation, a reference velocity of 0.5 m/s is set (based on the maximum velocities that appeared in the domain in previous computations) and the area of reference is the area of the domain. Therefore, in order to reduce the time step, the Courant number is going to be lowered. Numerical results of simulations with $C = 1$, $C = 0.1$, $C = 0.01$ and $C = 0.001$ can be seen in figure 3.25.

The results are rather interesting: the shape of the bubble shows a strong dependence on the time step of the simulation. In the first three pictures it looks like the solution is converging towards the desired shape shown in figure 3.22, however, reducing the time step one more order of magnitude leads to a solution where the bubble is too spherical. Therefore, it looks like as $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, the circularity of the bubble $\phi \rightarrow 1$, which is something that should not be happening.

To explain this, one should take a look at the stability parameter for each simulation. As previously mentioned, the recommended value for this multiphase solver is between 0.1 and 0.05, however, simulations with $C = 10^{-2}$ and $C = 10^{-3}$ have a stability parameter of 6×10^{-3} and 6×10^{-4} ,

Figure 3.25: Rising bubble, test case 1: Courant number comparison at $t = 3$. All computations were made with an interface thickness of 3, a mobility of 0.06 and a lattice resolution of 0.01 m .

way below the recommended limit, so these computations should not be considered accurate and the convergence to a spherical bubble is kind of artificial.

From the computations above, the only one with a stability parameter between the recommended values is the case with a Courant number of 0.1, so, in theory, it is the one that should have given the best result. Now, to see if the lattice resolution can also affect (and hopefully improve) the final form of the bubble, another series of computations was made with a Courant number of 0.1, but this time with different lattice resolutions. The results are shown in figure 3.26.

Again, something surprising happens: finer lattices seem to give worst results. To see why this occurs one should take a look at the simulation parameters in the following table:

Case	a	b	c	d
Resolution	1/40	1/80	1/160	1/320
Δt	10^{-4}	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Stab. param.	0.025	0.05	0.1	0.2

Table 3.5: Simulation parameters for the simulations with different resolutions.

Figure 3.26: Rising bubble, test case 1: lattice resolution comparison at $t = 3$. All computations were made with an interface thickness of 3, a mobility of 0.06 and a Courant number $C = 0.1$.

The data in this table shows a clear correlation between the stability parameter and the shape of the bubble, where a lower value of the stability parameter gives a more circular shape, just as expected from the results of the comparison between different Courant numbers (figure 3.25). From here, one might think that the shape of the bubble is completely determined by the stability parameter, meaning that, even for different resolutions, if the value of the stability parameter is kept constant, the same result should be obtained. To test this hypothesis, one last set of simulations was performed: different lattice resolutions were used, but changing the time step so that the stability parameter was kept the same in all of them, meaning that, if the hypothesis is true, the shape of the bubble should be almost identical in all cases. Results can be seen in figure 3.27.

This clearly shows that keeping the stability parameter constant does not imply that the shape will be the same at all resolutions, it definitely helps, but the resolution also has its influence on the final solution.

Overall, it was decided that the best result was this last one, with a stability parameter of 0.025, because, even if it is a little bit below the recommended values, it helps a lot to maintain the shape of the bubble, even with finer meshes. Therefore, the benchmark quantities are going to be computed for the simulation corresponding to figure 3.27c.

Figure 3.27: Rising bubble, test case 1: lattice resolution comparison keeping the stability parameter at 0.025. All computations were made with an interface thickness of 3 and a mobility of 0.06.

3.2.3.2 Benchmark of the numerical results

The center of mass position, rise velocity and circularity of the bubble are calculated in intervals of 0.1 s. The obtained results are displayed in the following graphs and compared with the reference data from [25].

Figure 3.28: Rising bubble, test case 1: Benchmark quantities

The first two graphs (center of mass and rise velocity) show very good agreement between the results of XFlow and the reference data from the other three groups, especially for the center of mass.

Figure 3.29: Circularity.

In the case of the rise velocity, XFlow slightly underestimates the correct value from $t = 0.5$ s and onwards, probably due to the formation of the two filaments, which are slower parts of the bubble and, thus, lower its overall speed.

Where the disagreement between XFlow and the other simulations gets more clear is when one takes a look at the circularity. XFlow predicts a value that tends to 0.75, while the correct circularity should be around 0.92. This difference is no surprise, though, since it is the immediate consequence of obtaining a bubble that is not elliptical in its shape.

It is important to note that the continuous variations in the value of the circularity are a consequence of the method used to measure the perimeter of the bubble. More details about how the benchmark quantities have been computed using XFlow can be found in appendix C.

Figure 3.30: Rising bubble, test case 2: previous results.

3.2.4 Test case 2

As seen in table 3.4, the second test case corresponds to a problem with a much higher density and viscosity ratio ($\rho_1/\rho_2 = 1000$ and $\mu_1/\mu_2 = 100$), which should lead to a bubble in the ellipsoidal-cap regime. The shape of the bubble at $t = 3$ s as obtained with other simulation codes in [25] can be seen in figure 3.30.

As observed, two filaments should appear at both sides of the bubble. Furthermore, a breakup on those filaments is expected to occur between $t = 2.2$ s and $t = 2.4$ s, even though not all codes managed to show this behavior.

3.2.4.1 Simulation setup

In the previous test case it was seen that the shape and evolution of the bubble greatly depends on the time step of the simulation, and even though the recommended stability parameter is between 0.05 and 0.1, better results were obtained outside of this range. In particular, it was observed that smaller time steps helped to prevent the bubble from deforming (so a small time step worked better for the test case 1), while larger time steps allowed the bubble to have a more developed shape. Because of this, it is expected that in this second test case a longer time step will work better, even outside of the recommended limits.

With this idea in mind, the first part in this test case is going to be to find a suitable time step which allows the bubble to develop a similar shape to the ones pictured in figure 3.30 and, ideally, show a breakup in the filaments around $t = 2.4$ s. Three different time steps were tested, which gave a stability parameter between 0.0974 (in the recommended interval) and 0.974 (way

over the recommended values and very close to 1). All the simulations were performed with the default values for the mobility and interface thickness ($I=3$ and $M=0.02$) and a lattice resolution of $1/80$ ($0.0125 m$). The results are compared in figure 3.31.

As observed, the simulation with the recommended stability parameter gave the worst results: the shape of the bubble is too “static” and no filaments are formed. The second simulation, with a time step 5 times larger, allowed the formation of two small filaments, but they vanished very fast (probably due to diffusion) and no breakup was observed. Finally, the last simulation, with a time step 10 times longer than the first one and a stability parameter of 0.974, has given the best results: not only are the filaments formed, but also a breakup seems to occur at $t = 2.4s$. To confirm this, a simulation with a more refined lattice was performed (with a time step that preserved the stability parameter at 0.974) and, sure enough, the breakup was observed. This simulation corresponds to the last row in figure 3.31.

Now that the “ideal” time step has been found, it is time to test the other parameters. The interface thickness is going to be set as 3 based on the results obtained in the previous test case, but the mobility has to be checked again. This time, simulations with $M = 0.001$, $M = 0.01$, $M = 0.02$ and $M = 0.06$ have been performed, with no higher values being tested because the computations turned unstable. The obtained results are displayed in figure 3.32.

From that images it is clear that higher values of mobility increase the diffusion between the two phases, making the filaments disappear before any breakup can occur (case with $M = 0.06$). As a consequence, lowering this value leads to filaments that remain longer in time, closer to the expected solution. However, the case with the lowest mobility ($M = 0.001$) developed some regions where the concentration was significantly higher than 1, something that is not realistic and meaning that such small values for the mobility should not be used. As a result, it was decided that the best case was the one with $M = 0.01$, being the smallest value tested that presented breakup without introducing errors in the concentration.

With this, all parameters are now set ($I = 3$, $M = 0.01$) and the final simulation can be performed. Again, the same computation will be made using different lattice resolutions, but ensuring that in all of them the stability parameter is kept the same ($Sp = 0.976$). The final results can be seen in figure 3.33.

As observed, all three simulations gave very similar results, but only the

Figure 3.31: Rising bubble, test case 2: comparison between different stability parameters. The first three rows show correspond to three different stability parameters, and show the evolution of the bubble at the time interval where the breakup is expected to happen. The last row is the same case as the third one, but with a more refined mesh. All computations were carried out with $I = 3$ and $M = 0.02$.

Figure 3.32: Rising bubble, test case 2: comparison between different mobilities. Every row corresponds to the evolution of the bubble with a different mobility value. All computations were made with a resolution of $1/160$ and keeping the stability parameter at 0.976

Figure 3.33: Rising bubble, test case 2: comparison between different lattice resolutions. A mobility of 0.001 was used and the stability parameter was kept around 0.976 in all three cases.

one with the highest resolution was able to correctly reproduce the breakup of the filaments, something which happens, as predicted, around $t = 2.4s$. For this reason, the simulation with the highest resolution is the one that is going to be used to compute the benchmark quantities.

3.2.4.2 Benchmark of the numerical results

Again, the center of mass position, rise velocity and circularity have been computed each 0.1s and are compared to the reference data from the three groups in [25].

Figure 3.34: Rising bubble, test case 2: benchmark quantities.

Just as in the first test case, XFlow predicts very well the position of the center of mass, which is in complete agreement with the reference data.

About the rise velocity, results are good overall, but between $t = 1.5$ and $t = 2.5$ there is a substantial decrease in the velocity, especially just before the breakup occurs, which is something not observed by the other groups. It is actually rather strange, because such a meaningful drop in velocity should also have its influence on the rise of the center of mass, but that does not seem to be the case.

Finally, the circularity is here in much better agreement with the reference data than it was in test case 1. The evolution predicted by XFlow is almost the same as the other groups until around $t = 2.3$, when the breakup occurs and an inflection point appears in the graph. What happens from this point is uncertain, because there is no agreement even between the reference simulations, so it is difficult to say if the results from XFlow are actually worse or not than the others.

3.2.5 Conclusions

Throughout this section the problem of a rising bubble has been simulated with a broad range of different parameters, and the final results are quite mixed, in the sense that their accuracy with respect to the reference data has not been good in all cases.

The new multiphase solver of XFlow has demonstrated that it can correctly track the position of the bubble during its ascent, since the center of mass position follows exactly the same behavior as in the reference data. However, the same cannot be said about other parameters.

Probably, the most important remark in these simulations is how dependent on the time step (and the stability parameter) is the shape of the bubble. All simulations have shown that lowering the time step in order to obtain a smaller stability parameter causes the bubble to be more circular, while simulations where the stability parameter is allowed to be higher tend to make a bubble with a more complex shape.

What this means is that one can obtain any shape in the diagram of figure 3.21 just by changing the time step, so that for every problem there is an “ideal” stability parameter that will give the desired results. This is something that should not happen or, at least, not to this extent, because the time step should not have such a big influence on the physics of the simulation.

Apart from this, the influence of other parameters in the final solution was also tested, like the mobility, which has shown that it can increase the

diffusion between the two phases (as expected from the Cahn-Hilliard equation) and that it helps to maintain a more circular shape in the bubble. Also, it was seen that for this kind of problem an interface thickness of 3 elements was enough to obtain a good solution.

3.3 Rayleigh-Taylor Instability

The second validation test for the multiphase solver is going to be the simulation of a Rayleigh-Taylor instability. This is a classic multiphase problem involving two fluids of different densities, where the heavier lies above of the less dense one and falls through it under the action of gravity or another acceleration.

This problem has already been studied with different numerical methods in a series of previous articles [56], [19], [12], and by XFlow itself with its other multiphase solver. Therefore, there is a good amount of data with which to compare the results of the current simulation.

3.3.1 Case description

The case that is going to be simulated was first introduced by Tryggvason in [56], and consists on a rectangular domain of dimensions $[-d/2, d/2] \times [-2d, 2d]$ where two layers of fluid coexist, initially at rest and separated by an interface

$$\eta(x) = -0.1d \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{d}\right), \quad (3.14)$$

as seen in figure 3.35.

Figure 3.35: Computational domain for the simulation of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability. Picture taken from the XFlow validation guide [54].

In this geometry, free-slip boundary conditions are imposed in the vertical walls, while no-slip conditions are enforced at the top and bottom horizontal walls.

This problem can be characterized with two nondimensional quantities: The Atwood and the Reynolds number. The former gives an idea of the

density ratio between the two fluids, and was defined by Tryggvason as

$$At = \frac{\rho_A - \rho_B}{\rho_A + \rho_B}, \quad (3.15)$$

where ρ_A is the density of the fluid on top.

On the other side, the Reynolds number for this kind of problem was defined by Guermond and Quartapelle in [19] as

$$Re = \frac{\rho_B d^{3/2} g^{3/2}}{\mu}, \quad (3.16)$$

where ρ_B is the density of the fluid at the bottom, d is the length parameter, g the gravitational acceleration and μ the dynamic viscosity, which is assumed to be the same on both fluids. The present case is going to be solved for $At = 0.5$ (density ratio 3) and $Re = 1000$.

It should be noted that the initial study by Tryggvason [56] considered inviscid fluids. It was Guermond and Quartapelle [19] (and later Ding et al. [12]) who later took into account the effects of viscosity and introduced the Reynolds number. None of them considered the surface tension between the fluids.

Apart from this, Tryggvason defined a nondimensional time scale \bar{t} as

$$\bar{t} = t\sqrt{gAt}, \quad (3.17)$$

where t is the “real” time. This scale is going to be used to compare the results from the different simulations.

3.3.2 Benchmark quantities

To validate the results from the simulation, some quantities have to be measured and compared with previous results. For the case of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability, the typical requested data is the position of both the lower part of the dense fluid (spike) and the higher part of the lighter fluid (bubble). A typical graph of the evolution of these two positions can be seen in figure 3.36.

3.3.3 Simulation setup

As previously stated, the nondimensional numbers for this case are $At = 0.5$ and $Re = 1000$, which correspond to the following choice of physical

Figure 3.36: Typical evolution of spike and bubble positions. Image taken from Ref. [56].

parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d &= 1 \text{ m}, \\
 \rho_A &= 3000 \text{ kg/m}^3, \\
 \rho_B &= 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3, \\
 \mu_A &= \mu_B = 1 \text{ Pa s}, \\
 g &= 1 \text{ m/s}^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, the multiphase solver in XFlow needs values for the following parameters:

- Surface tension.** It was already mentioned that none of the previous studies had taken into account surface tension effects. However, this parameter is needed for the computations in XFlow. To find the most suitable value, a series of simulations were performed for surface tensions of 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} N/m, and the obtained results were all *identical*. Then, not having any preferred value, it was selected a surface tension of 10^{-2} N/m because it is in the order of magnitude of water, which has a similar density to the considered fluids.
- Contact angle.** The contact angle is needed for the surface tension model and represents the angle that forms the surface of a droplet when adhered to a solid wall. Since in the present case all the domain is filled with liquid, this parameter will have no influence on the simulation.

(a) Spike and bubble evolution for different interface thickness compared with the results from Ding (solid line), Guermond and Quartapelle (triangles) and Tryggvason (diamonds).

(b) Numerical results at $\bar{t} = 2.5$. From left to right: $I = 1$, $I = 1.5$, $I = 3$ and $I = 5$.

Figure 3.37: Interface thickness comparison. All computations carried out with mobility = 0.02 in a lattice of 200×800 elements.

The default value of 30° was left. (Actually, to confirm this, different values were tested, but there was no difference in the results).

- **Interface thickness.** This parameter represents the number of lattice elements used to model the interface between the two fluids. The default value is 3, but several values were tested as seen in figure 3.37.

It can be observed that a thinner interface allows a “more free” behavior and a faster fall of the fluid (closer to Ding’s solution), with the formation of more complex structures. However, if it is too thin, the diffusion between the two phases appears higher than normal (it can be seen by the gradient of colors in the left picture of figure 3.37b).

Because of this, an interface thickness value of 1.5 was selected, since it allows the fluid to fall faster while not having problems with high diffusion.

- **Mobility.** This is a constant in the Cahn-Hilliard equation (1.111) that controls the diffusion between the two phases. The recommended

(a) Spike and bubble evolution for different mobilities compared with the results from Ding (solid line), Guermont and Quartapelle (triangles) and Trygvason (diamonds).

(b) Numerical results at $\bar{t} = 2.5$. From left to right: $M = 0.001$, $M = 0.02$, $M = 0.06$ and $M = 0.1$.

Figure 3.38: Mobility comparison. All computations carried out with an interface thickness of 1.5 in a lattice of 200×800 elements.

value in XFlow is 0.02, but other values between 0.001 and 0.1 were tested and are compared in figure 3.38. Values over 0.12 led to unstable simulations.

It can be seen that a higher mobility helps to maintain a more uniform solution, but at the price of having a slower spike and bubble. A high mobility leads, then, to a shape that is more similar to the solution of Ding but to a rise and fall velocities slower than they should.

Choosing the right mobility is, therefore, a balance between those two factors. The selected value was finally 0.06 because it maintains a shape more similar to the one found in previous articles and it does not slow down the fall of the spike (even though the rise of the bubble is affected).

To summarize, the final benchmark simulation was performed with surface tension $\sigma = 10^{-2}$ N/m, a contact angle $\alpha = 30^\circ$, an interface thickness $I = 1.5$ and a mobility $M = 0.06$.

(a) Spike and bubble evolution for different lattice resolutions compared with the results from Ding (solid line), Guermond and Quartapelle (triangles) and Tryggvason (diamonds).

(b) Numerical results at $\bar{t} = 2.5$. Lattice resolutions are, from left to right: 50×200 , 100×400 , 200×800 and 400×1600 .

Figure 3.39: Lattice resolution comparison. All computations carried out with an interface thickness of 1.5 and a mobility of 0.06.

3.3.4 Numerical results

Now that all the parameters are fixed the final computation can be presented. For comparison purposes the simulation was ran on four lattices of different resolution and their corresponding time step:

The stability parameter is a quantity calculated by XFlow at each time step to give a measure of the stability of the simulation. In this case, ideal values are between 0.1 and 0.05.

From the results, it is clear that the resolution of the mesh has a big impact in the final result. Finer lattices allow the formation of more complex structures and make the spike and bubble fall and rise faster, respectively. However, none of them has managed to accurately reproduce the solution found by Tryggvason, Guermond & or Ding, the rise and fall are always slower than they should as seen in figures 3.39a and 3.40, where only the best result is shown.

Lattice resolution (cm)	Lattice resolution (cells)	Time step (s)	Stability parameter
5	50×200	$1.42 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$\sim 0.008 - 0.1$
1	100×400	$2.87 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$\sim 0.043 - 0.085$
0.5	200×800	$1.44 \cdot 10^{-4}$	~ 0.086
0.25	400×1600	$7.21 \cdot 10^{-5}$	~ 0.171

Table 3.6: Simulation parameters for each case.

Figure 3.40: Rayleigh-Taylor instability: final results. The best solution obtained with XFlow is compared against the reference data from Ding (solid line), Guermond and Quartapelle (triangles) and Tryggvason (diamonds).

Figure 3.41: Time evolution of the domain for the case of a lattice of 400×1600 elements.

3.3.5 Conclusions

As seen in the presented results, certain parameters like interface thickness and mobility, which are not necessarily related to the physical properties of the fluids, have a very important effect on the outcome of the simulation. The correct choice of these parameters is, then, critical to obtain an accurate solution, and more work should be done in order to find the ideal values for general applications.

On the other side, none of the performed computations has reproduced the solutions found in [56], [19], [12], which are all very similar, even with coarser meshes as the ones used here. This probably means that there is something that needs some more fine tuning, but it is not something unexpected from a multiphase solver that is still in active development.

It should be noted, however, that the other available multiphase solver in XFlow does correctly reproduce the position of the spike and the bubble.

Conclusions

Throughout this document an extensive presentation of the validation tests carried out with XFlow has been made. Each simulation has managed to expose both strengths and weaknesses of the different solvers used, and also some unexpected results.

Especially curious are, for example, the stochastic behavior of the thermal solver and the enormous dependence that the shape of the bubble has with the time step and the stability parameter.

Overall, the less satisfying results were obtained with the new multiphase solver, since neither the rising bubble nor the Rayleigh-Taylor benchmarks can be qualified as passed. Special attention should be paid towards modifying the solver so that the bubble shape is correct without using “artificial” time steps, and also towards making the spike and bubble of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability fall and rise at the correct speed.

Apart from this, further study should be made to better understand the role that the interface thickness and mobility play in the simulation, because, as seen during this work, different values gave better results depending on the test case simulated.

On the other side, the more mature, single phase, thermal solver gave, in general, a more solid set of results. The predicted velocity profiles were in very good agreement with the experimental data, as well as many of the temperature profiles and even the frequency of the thermal fluctuations.

However, not everything was positive either. It was seen that in some profiles XFlow tends to greatly overestimate the temperatures, and it was not completely clear whether refining the lattice actually helps in bringing the solution closer to reality, because while going from 4 mm to 2 mm was an improvement, the next lattice with a resolution of 1 mm in the mixing area gave worst results.

About this, it is a shame that complete 16 seconds computations with a resolution of 1 mm in the whole domain could not be made, because that

would have been a very good comparison against the other simulations with 4 and 2 millimeters. Contrary to this, the finest resolution that we were able to test was only partially refined to 1 mm, could only be computed for 10 s, required a smaller time step and was initialized with a different method, so, probably, it is not a good comparison against the other simulations.

Finally, even if improvements can still be made, XFlow shows that the lattice Boltzmann method is a strong alternative to the classical numerical methods in CFD, and its advantages like full parallelizability and no need to create a specific mesh for each problem have been experienced (and very welcomed) by the author.

Appendix A

Velocity Profile Corrections

As seen in table 3.1, the measured flow rates in the cold and hot inlet were 9 l/s and 6 l/s respectively. However, the imposed velocity profiles as boundary conditions underestimated the real flow rates. To fix this situation, a constant velocity was added to each velocity profile so that the correct flow rate was recovered. This is how it was calculated:

Let us define the following quantities:

- C_0 : the initial, underestimated flow rate from the original velocity profile.
- \bar{C} : the correct flow rate as measured by the flowmeters.
- S : surface of the pipe section.

The average velocity V for a given flow rate C in a pipe with section S is given by

$$V = \frac{C}{S}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Therefore, the increment in velocity needed to correct the flow rate can be calculated as

$$\Delta V = \frac{\Delta C}{S} = \frac{\bar{C} - C_0}{S}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

This gives, for each inlet:

$$\Delta V_{InCo} = \frac{(9 - 8.555)10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}}{\pi 0.07^2 \text{ m}^2} \sim 0.029 \text{ m/s}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\Delta V_{InHo} = \frac{(6 - 5.687)10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}}{\pi 0.05^2 \text{ m}^2} \sim 0.040 \text{ m/s}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Appendix B

Heat Transfer Coefficient

The heat transfer for a material of a certain thickness that is between two different media (e.g. water at one side and air at the other) can be approximated as [1]

$$\text{HTC} = \left(\frac{1}{\text{HTC}_1} + \frac{dx_w}{k} + \frac{1}{\text{HTC}_2} \right)^{-1}, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where HTC_1 and HTC_2 are the heat transfer coefficient of the medium on each side, and dx_w and k are the wall thickness and the thermal conductivity of the material.

In our case, the pipe wall is 1 cm thick and made of Plexiglas, which has a $k = 0.19 \text{ W/mK}$, and we have water on the inside and air on the outside, which have HTC's of

$$\begin{aligned} \text{HTC}_{\text{water}} &\sim 1000 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K} \\ \text{and } \text{HTC}_{\text{air}} &\sim 50 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}, \end{aligned}$$

estimated from the values found in [1].

Therefore, the HTC of the Plexiglas wall can be approximated as

$$\text{HTC}_{\text{Plexiglas}} = \left(\frac{1}{\text{HTC}_{\text{water}}} + \frac{dx_w}{k} + \frac{1}{\text{HTC}_{\text{air}}} \right)^{-1} \sim 13.6 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Appendix C

Rising Bubble Benchmark Quantities

Calculating the center of mass position, rise velocity and circularity is not a trivial task. To be able to compute or estimate these quantities two key tools of XFlow were used: creating custom fields and calculating volume integrals.

- Custom fields: Once a simulation has finished, XFlow allows the creation of custom scalar fields in the computational domain. They can be created as a function of the default fields, the position, etc. and even *if* conditional statements can be used.
- Volume integrals: Another functionality of XFlow is the ability to calculate volume integrals of a given scalar field in the whole domain-

Here is how these tools were used to calculate each quantity:

- Center of mass

The center of mass of the bubble is defined as

$$\mathbf{X}_c = (x_c, y_c) = \frac{\int_{\Omega_2} \mathbf{x} dx}{\int_{\Omega_2} 1 dx}. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

The first thing that one has to notice is that, since the bubble only rises vertically (y direction), the x coordinate of the center of mass is always 0, so only the y component has to be found.

Figure C.1: Custom field for the center of mass.

To calculate this integral in a discretized domain, one needs to know the y component of all the lattice points in which the bubble is located and then do a summation of all the values.

To isolate the bubble and know the y component of each point, the following custom field is defined:

$$[\text{if}((\text{vof} < 0.8), y, 0)], \quad (\text{C.2})$$

which means that in all the points where the VOF is less than 0.8 the field should have the value of the y component of its position, and be 0 if the condition is not satisfied. By doing this we have filtered the position of the bubble and part of the interface (results were better with more interface, hence why there is a 0.8 and not a 0.5), as seen in figure C.1.

Now, by simply doing a normalized volume integral of this field, the y component of the center of mass is found.

- Rise velocity

Figure C.2: Custom field for the rise velocity.

The rise velocity is defined as the y component of

$$\mathbf{U}_c = \frac{\int_{\Omega_2} \mathbf{u} dx}{\int_{\Omega_2} 1 dx}, \quad (\text{C.3})$$

and to find this quantity the same approach as for the center of mass can be used. We define, then, the following field:

$$[\text{if}((\text{vof} < 0.8), vy, 0)], \quad (\text{C.4})$$

which is the same as before, but now with the y component of the velocity, as seen in figure C.2.

Again, doing now a normalized volume integral of this field will give the rise velocity of the bubble.

- Circularity

The circularity, defined as

$$\phi = \frac{P_a}{P_b} = \frac{\text{perimeter of area-equivalent circle}}{\text{perimeter of bubble}} = \frac{\pi d_a}{P_b}, \quad (\text{C.5})$$

is probably the most tricky quantity to calculate, because it involves measuring the perimeter of the bubble, and the only tools available are creating custom fields and calculating integrals.

Figure C.3: Custom field for the circularity.

The method that was found is the following: create a custom field filtering only the interface and use a volume integral as a way to calculate how many lattice points are in the interface. In this way, the perimeter of the bubble is directly proportional to the number of points.

Also, it should be noted that if the area of the bubble is assumed constant during its evolution, then the perimeter of the area-equivalent circle is also constant and equal to the initial perimeter of the bubble. Therefore, by normalizing the number of lattice points in the interface with the lattice points in the interface at $t = 0$ we will have the inverse of the circularity.

The defined custom field is the following:

$$[\text{if}((\text{vof} > 0.1) * (\text{vof} < 0.9), 1, 0)], \quad (\text{C.6})$$

where $*$ is equivalent to an AND statement. This field gives as a result what is seen in figure C.3.

Now, doing a volume integral of this field will give a very similar value (which we call a) during the first time steps, this is the value that we have to use to normalize the volume integral. In order to do so, we can modify the field so that the result is already normalized:

$$[\text{if}((\text{vof} > 0.1) * (\text{vof} < 0.9), 1/a, 0)]. \quad (\text{C.7})$$

As we said, the volume integral of this field will be the inverse of the circularity so, the values just have to be imported to a text file and inverted.

One important thing to notice is that this way of calculating the circularity is very dependent on the lattice resolution. This comes from the fact that it is based on “counting” how many points are in the interface and, therefore, the higher the resolution is, more stable will be the number of points. This is why there are oscillations in the graphs of the circularity.

Another important fact is that choosing an interval of VOF between 0.1 and 0.9 gave better results than smaller intervals like 0.3-0.6 because the number of points in the interface was also more stable and the oscillations were less severe.

Bibliography

- [1] Overall heat transfer coefficient. http://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/overall-heat-transfer-coefficient-d_434.html.
- [2] Tarik Al-Shemmeri. *Engineering fluid mechanics*. Bookboon, 2012.
- [3] Santosh Ansumali and Iliya V Karlin. Entropy function approach to the lattice Boltzmann method. *Journal of statistical physics*, 107(1-2):291–308, 2002.
- [4] E Aslan, A Nahavandi, I Taymaz, and AC Benim. A Study on Representing Irregular Boundaries by the Lattice Boltzmann Method.
- [5] Peter Brookes. Lattice Boltzmann in the Finite Knudsen Number Flow Regime. Master’s thesis, University of Melbourne, Australia, 2009.
- [6] Carlo Cercignani. *The Boltzmann Equation and Its Applications*. Springer-Verlag, 1988.
- [7] B Chun and AJC Ladd. Interpolated boundary condition for lattice Boltzmann simulations of flows in narrow gaps. *Physical Review E*, 75(6):066705, 2007.
- [8] Roland Clift, John R Grace, and Martin E Weber. *Bubbles, drops, and particles*. Courier Corporation, 2005.
- [9] Paul J Dellar. Lattice and discrete Boltzmann equations for fully compressible flow. *Computational Fluid and Solid Mechanics*, pages 632–635, 2005.
- [10] Paul J Dellar. Lattice Boltzmann algorithms without cubic defects in Galilean invariance on standard lattices. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 259:270–283, 2014.

- [11] Dominique d’Humières. Multiple-relaxation-time lattice Boltzmann models in three dimensions. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 360(1792):437–451, 2002.
- [12] Hang Ding, Peter DM Spelt, and Chang Shu. Diffuse interface model for incompressible two-phase flows with large density ratios. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 226(2):2078–2095, 2007.
- [13] F Ducros, F Nicoud, and T Poinso. Wall-adapting local eddy-viscosity models for simulations in complex geometries. In *International Conference on Computational Conference*, pages 293–300, 1998.
- [14] E. Orlandini, M. R. Swift, J. M. Yeomans. A Lattice Boltzmann Model of Binary Fluid Mixtures. *Europhysics Letters*, 32(6):463, 2008.
- [15] Olga Filippova and Dieter Hänel. Grid refinement for lattice-BGK models. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 147(1):219–228, 1998.
- [16] Uriel Frisch, Brosl Hasslacher, and Yves Pomeau. Lattice-gas automata for the Navier-Stokes equation. *Physical review letters*, 56(14):1505, 1986.
- [17] Denis Gebauer, Matthias Kellermeier, Julian D Gale, Lennart Bergström, and Helmut Cölfen. Pre-nucleation clusters as solute precursors in crystallisation. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 43(7):2348–2371, 2014.
- [18] U Gerland, F Drube, and M Weber. Statistical mechanics ii, Spring Semester 2011.
- [19] J-L Guermond and L Quartapelle. A projection FEM for variable density incompressible flows. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 165(1):167–188, 2000.
- [20] Xiaoyi He, Shiyi Chen, and Gary D. Doolen. A Novel Thermal Model for the Lattice Boltzmann Method in Incompressible Limit. *J. Comput. Phys.*, 146(1):282–300, October 1998.
- [21] Xiaoyi He, Shiyi Chen, and Raoyang Zhang. A lattice Boltzmann scheme for incompressible multiphase flow and its application in simulation of Rayleigh–Taylor instability. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 152(2):642–663, 1999.

- [22] Xiaoyi He, Li-Shi Luo, and Micah Dembo. Some progress in lattice Boltzmann method. Part I. Nonuniform mesh grids. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 129(2):357–363, 1996.
- [23] Vincent Heuveline, Mathias J Krause, and Jonas Latt. Towards a hybrid parallelization of lattice Boltzmann methods. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 58(5):1071–1080, 2009.
- [24] D Holman, R Brionnaud, M Chavez, and E Valero. Aerodynamic Analysis of the 2nd High Lift Prediction Workshop by a Lattice-Boltzmann Method Solver. In *32nd AIAA Applied Aerodynamics Conference*, 2014.
- [25] S Hysing, S Turek, D Kuzmin, N Parolini, E Burman, S Ganesan, and L Tobiska. *Proposal for quantitative benchmark computations of bubble dynamics*. Univ., 2007.
- [26] Frank Incropera and David DeWitt. *Introduction to heat transfer*. 1985.
- [27] J. Latt, B. Chopard, O. Malaspinas, M. Deville, and A. Michler. Straight velocity boundaries in the lattice Boltzmann method. *Physical Review E*, 77(056703), 2008.
- [28] ST Jayaraju, EMJ Komen, and E Baglietto. Suitability of wall-functions in large eddy simulation for thermal fatigue in a T-junction. *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, 240(10):2544–2554, 2010.
- [29] Mehran Kardar. *Statistical physics of particles*. Cambridge University Press, 2007.
- [30] IV Karlin, D Sichau, and SS Chikatamarla. Consistent two-population lattice Boltzmann model for thermal flows. *Physical Review E*, 88(6):063310, 2013.
- [31] Takeshi Kataoka and Michihisa Tsutahara. Lattice Boltzmann method for the compressible Euler equations. *Physical review E*, 69(5):056702, 2004.
- [32] LD Landau and EM Lifshitz. *Course of theoretical physics - Mechanics, vol. 1*. Pergamon Press, 1976.
- [33] Shaofan Li and Wing Kam Liu. Meshfree and particle methods and their applications. *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, 55(1):1–34, 2002.

- [34] Guy R McNamara, Alejandro L Garcia, and Berni J Alder. A hydrodynamically correct thermal lattice Boltzmann model. *Journal of statistical physics*, 87(5-6):1111–1121, 1997.
- [35] Joel Moore. Physics 212: Statistical mechanics ii - lecture notes, Fall Semester 2010.
- [36] BT Nadiga. An Euler solver based on locally adaptive discrete velocities. *Journal of statistical physics*, 81(1-2):129–146, 1995.
- [37] Jun Ni, Yongxiang Zhang, Ching-Long Lin, and Shaowen Wang. Parallelization of a lattice Boltzmann method for lid-driven cavity flow. *UI research booth, Supercomputing*, 2003.
- [38] XF Pan, Aiguo Xu, Guangcai Zhang, and Song Jiang. Lattice Boltzmann approach to high-speed compressible flows. *International Journal of Modern Physics C*, 18(11):1747–1764, 2007.
- [39] Chen Peng. The Lattice Boltzmann Method for Fluid Dynamics: Theory and Applications. Master’s thesis, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Switzerland.
- [40] Kannan N Premnath and Sanjoy Banerjee. On the three-dimensional central moment lattice Boltzmann method. *Journal of Statistical Physics*, 143(4):747–794, 2011.
- [41] Y. H. Qian and S. A. Orszag. Lattice BGK Models for the Navier-Stokes Equation: Nonlinear Deviation in Compressible Regimes. *EPL (Europhysics Letters)*, 21(3):255, 1993.
- [42] N. Fueyo S. Izquierdo. Characteristic nonreflecting boundary conditions for open boundaries in lattice Boltzmann methods. *Physical Review E*, 78(046707), 2008.
- [43] Xiaowen Shan. Simulation of Rayleigh-Bénard convection using a lattice Boltzmann method. *Physical Review E*, 55(3):2780, 1997.
- [44] Tsan-Hsing Shih, Louis A Povinelli, Nan-Suey Liu, Mark G Potapczuk, and JL Lumley. *A generalized wall function*. National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Glenn Research Center, 1999.

- [45] C Shu, YT Chew, and XD Niu. Least-squares-based lattice Boltzmann method: a meshless approach for simulation of flows with complex geometry. *Physical Review E*, 64(4):045701, 2001.
- [46] BL Smith, JH Mahaffy, and K Angele. A CFD benchmarking exercise based on flow mixing in a T-junction. *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, 264:80–88, 2013.
- [47] BL Smith, JH Mahaffy, K Angele, and J Westin. Report of the OECD/NEA-Vattenfall T-junction Benchmark exercise. *NEA/CSNI Report*, 2011.
- [48] MIT Student. Lecture 38: Nucleation and spinodal decomposition.
- [49] Sauro Succi. *The Lattice Boltzmann Equation for Fluid Dynamics and Beyond*. Oxford University Press, 2001.
- [50] Sauro Succi, Iliya V Karlin, and Hudong Chen. Colloquium: Role of the H theorem in lattice Boltzmann hydrodynamic simulations. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 74(4):1203, 2002.
- [51] Sauro Succi, Nasrollah Moradi, Andreas Greiner, and Simone Melchionna. Lattice Boltzmann modeling of water-like fluids. *Frontiers in Physics*, 2:22, 2014.
- [52] Succi, S. and Sbragaglia, M. and Ubertini, S. . Lattice Boltzmann Method. *Scholarpedia*, 5(5):9507, 2010. revision 131114.
- [53] Michael R Swift, E Orlandini, WR Osborn, and JM Yeomans. Lattice Boltzmann simulations of liquid-gas and binary fluid systems. *Physical Review E*, 54(5):5041, 1996.
- [54] Next Limit Technologies. *XFlow Validation Guide (v92)*. 2014.
- [55] Next Limit Technologies. *XFlow User Guide (v94)*. 2015.
- [56] Grétar Tryggvason. Numerical simulations of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 75(2):253–282, 1988.
- [57] V. M. Kendon, M. E. Cates, J-C. Desplat, I. Pagonabarraga, P. Bladon. Inertial effects in three-dimensional spinodal decomposition of a symmetric binary fluid mixture: a lattice Boltzmann study. *J. Fluid Mech.*, 440:147–203, 2001.

- [58] W. Daniel Hillis. Richard Feynman and The Connection Machine. *Physics Today*, 440:42, 1989.
- [59] Alexander J. Wagner. *A Practical Introduction to the Lattice Boltzmann Method*. North Dakota State University, 2008.
- [60] Dieter A. Wolf-Gladrow. *Lattice-Gas Cellular Automata and Lattice Boltzmann Models - An Introduction*. Springer, 2005.
- [61] Xiaoyi He, Li-Shi Luo. Lattice Boltzmann Model for the Incompressible Navier-Stokes Equation. *Jour. Stat. Physics*, 88(3-4):927–944, 1997.
- [62] Lin Zheng, Song Zheng, and Qinglan Zhai. Lattice Boltzmann equation method for the Cahn-Hilliard equation. *Physical Review E*, 91(1):013309, 2015.
- [63] Qisu Zou and Xiaoyi He. On pressure and velocity boundary conditions for the lattice Boltzmann BGK model. *Physics of Fluids (1994-present)*, 9(6):1591–1598, 1997.